

CWPharma
CLEAR WATERS FROM PHARMACEUTICALS

Evaluation and experiences of full-scale ozonation followed by MBBR post-treatment at Kalundborg wastewater treatment plant

GoA3.2: Flexible use of existing infrastructure

November 2020

EUROPEAN
REGIONAL
DEVELOPMENT
FUND

KOMPETENZZENTRUM
WasserBerlin

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Introduction

Background

CWPharma (Clear Waters from Pharmaceuticals) is a project funded by the EU Interreg Baltic Sea region Programme. The project will provide tools and recommendations to policy makers, authorities and municipalities on the best ways to reduce emissions of pharmaceuticals in the Baltic Sea Region. In work package 3 (WP3), advanced treatment to reduce pharmaceuticals from wastewater was studied.

Besides treatment with activated carbon, ozonation is one of the main technologies for removing pharmaceuticals from wastewater. Ozone has strong oxidizing properties that can degrade pharmaceuticals and other poorly degradable substances in wastewater. With its strong oxidizing properties, the pharmaceuticals can be transformed to less active by-products. Ozonation is usually followed by biological post-treatment to remove biodegradable transformation and oxidation by-products, which in the case of Kalundborg, is a full-scale moving bed biofilm reactor (MBBR).

The ozonation plant at Kalundborg wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) was implemented in 2003 and constructed in order to treat inert COD from the industrial wastewater coming into Kalundborg WWTP. The inert COD originates from the inactivation of genetically modified biomass of the local biotech industries. Originally, the inactivation process consisted of heat and lime inactivation resulting in Maillard reactions and, thus, high concentrations of non-biologically degradable organic material (> 400 mg COD/l). Later, the inactivation process was changed to heat only, which resulted in decreased COD concentrations of approximately 280 mg/l. Finally, the inactivation process was further changed to the usage of lime in order to achieve a pH > 11. This resulted in a further decrease in COD concentrations to a level near 150 mg/l, which is the present level. At the present level, adsorption processes in the activated sludge plant are enough to remove the inert COD and achieve an effluent concentration of approximately 40-60 mg/l.

Due to this history, the ozonation plant at Kalundborg WWTP has a production capacity several times higher than required for only API removal. This fact has been a challenge in relation to optimizing API removal in CWPharma, since the ozone doses were several times greater than necessary, which would have resulted in high operational costs. However, this has to a large extent been solved within the CWPharma project by retrofitting the existing ozone plant.

Activities

The main objective of the study was the evaluation and process optimization of the full-scale ozonation system at the Kalundborg WWTP to retrofit the system for low ozone dosage necessary for API removal from the previous high ozone dose used for inert COD removal. This objective included the following activities:

- Evaluation and retrofitting of the full-scale ozonation system
- Testing possibilities for using an optical COD sensor for of the ozonation plant for stable and economic pharmaceutical removal with regards to online COD sensor
- Monitoring of relevant APIs
- Monitoring of ozonation by-products (e.g. bromate formation) and formation of API transformation products
- Lab-scale MBBR experiment to verify the potential and kinetics for API and transformation product removal
- Conducting a risk assessment to evaluate the toxicity for marine water from possible by-products potentially formed in ozonation

The evaluation of the potential options to optimize the MBBR operation was primarily done by AU in lab-scale reactors due to considerations to the full-scale plant with respect to effluent water quality from the MBBR plant.

Description of the wastewater treatment plant in Kalundborg

Kalundborg Municipal WWTP is designed for 50.000 PE capacity. However, due to the high (approximately 35 °C) temperature of the incoming industrial wastewater, the capacity is closer to 200.000 PE. Approximately 60 % of the flow to the WWTP originates from local industries, thus the wastewater composition is heavily affected by the large industrial flow to the plant. The WWTP is a classical BIODENIPHO plant with a side stream hydrolysis. An overview of the plant is seen on the following Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview picture of Kalundborg WWTP.

The plant consists of a mechanical pre-treatment with grid and sand removal. Hereafter the water is pumped to the anaerobic pre-tanks in front of the alternating ditches. From the anaerobic pre-tanks the wastewater and return sludge is directed to the ditches. Originally the ditches were operated as two sets of alternating ditches with two tanks in each set. However, due to hydraulic challenges, the alternating operation has been omitted and the plant is operated as four tanks in parallel with an equal flow directed to each tank. From the ditches the total flow is collected in a well, where it is divided for the secondary clarifiers. In the well, iron chloride for phosphorus precipitation is added. From the clarifiers, the sludge is directed to the sludge pumping station, where both the return sludge pumps and activated sludge pumps are located. The return sludge pumps return the sludge to the side-stream hydrolysis and the anaerobic pre-tanks. The activated sludge pumps direct the activated sludge to the sludge dewatering where it is dewatered to a concentration of 22 % DS content. The dewatered sludge is spread on agricultural land as fertilizer. After the secondary clarifiers the water can be directed to the tertiary treatment, including an ozonation plant and a MBBR plant used as post-treatment. Finally, WWTP effluent is pumped to the other side of the road and from thereon, pumped to the recipient (not shown in Figure 1). A schematic overview of the WWTP is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic overview of Kalundborg WWTP.

An overview of the water quality at the WWTP influent is shown in Table 1. Due to the nature of the COD received from the industries (mainly inert), the COD/BOD ratio of 4.2 is comparably high. However, nitrogen removal is not affected by this and the effluent demand for 8 mg/l TN is fulfilled, which can be explained by the long sludge age in the plant (> 30 days), which gives the hydrolysis process time to convert the slowly degradable parts of the organic matter into more easily degradable COD.

Table 1: Influent data for Kalundborg WWTP (2018 data).

Parameter	Average loading	Peak loading (85 % percentile)	Unit
Flow	17,110	21,258	m ³ /d
COD	5,163	6,182	kg/d
BOD	1,215	1,528	kg/d
TN	504	585	kg/d
TP	68	85	kg/d
COD/BOD		4.2	
COD/TN		10.2	
COD/TP		76	

The ozonation plant, originally designed for COD reduction, consists of two parallel lanes and can treat, in total, up to 1,200 m³/h. The two ozone generators, individually coupled to each line, can produce between 7.2 and 90 kgO₃/h, thereby allowing an ozone dosage between 12 and 150 mgO₃/l, which, with a DOC content around 15-17 mg/l, corresponds to a specific ozone dose between 0.75 and 9.4 mgO₃/mg DOC. Within CWPharma, liquid oxygen (LOX, 3 x 50 m³ tanks) was used as the oxygen supply of the ozone generators and the ozone was injected via a pump-injection system. Ozone reactions took place in three 50m³ tanks operated in series (150 m³ reactor volume per lane), providing a minimum hydraulic retention time of 15 minutes. Automatic process control can be used to define a setpoint (constant ozone dose) of the flow-proportional ozone dosage. The post-treatment consists of a moving bed bioreactor (MBBR) with a total volume of 1,200 m³ filled to 25 V-% with Kaldnes K1 carriers (600 m³/t surface area). Total reactor volume is divided into 4 zones which can be operated aerated or non-aerated. It is possible to adjust the pH and add ethanol as a COD source, however neither option was used during CWPharma project.

Residual ozone in the off gas of the tanks is removed by an ozone destructor unit so it only contains oxygen, which is later used in the hydrolysis tanks for aeration. The ozonation effluent is then treated in a MBBR reactor as a final nitrification and (if required) denitrification stage.

Evaluation of a full-scale ozonation system

Throughout the CWPharma project several retrofits to the ozonation plant were done prior to the operational start-up of the plant after several years of inactivity to ensure stable operation of the plant. The following was implemented in order to retrofit the existing ozonation plant and adapt it in order to be able to maintain API elimination in an optimized way:

- July 2018: Initial start-up after more than 7 years of inactivity
- August-September 2018: Maintenance of injection system and generators and switchboards
- October-November 2018: Optimization of pressure gauges and injection system as well as installation of new PLC
- April 2019: Decoupling of hydrogen peroxide system, purchase of LOX instead of production at VASP plant
- May 2019: Service on switchboard cooling system
- June 2019: Service on injection pumps

A major change was conducted with the installation of new PLCs (programmable logic controller) for the plant, which was done in November 2018. The installations of the PLCs were necessary to reach lower amounts of ozone production in each of the two ozone generators. With the installation complete, it was possible to reach a minimum ozone production of 5.2 kg O₃/h, corresponding to an introduced concentration of 8.6 mg O₃/l and a specific dosage of 0.52 mg O₃/mg DOC. This is the only alteration with the ozone system that resulted in a change of capacity, as the rest of the alterations were associated with reliability of the plant and maintaining a stable treatment. One control strategy tested at Kalundborg WWTP included controlling the ozone dosage based on the DOC content of the wastewater. In order to estimate the possibility of utilizing such a control strategy, a COD sensor from WTW (CarboVis[®]701) was tested to follow the daily variations. The reason for using a COD sensor was due to the relationship between COD and DOC. If a trustworthy DOC/COD ratio could be found, it would be possible to use the COD values. By tracking the COD value, a feed forward signal could be sent to the ozone generator and thereby regulate the amount of ozone produced. The main benefit of this strategy is to ensure that a setpoint for the specific ozone dose would always be maintained. Other benefits include potential energy savings, avoiding overdosing and possibly avoiding unwanted bromate formation, depending on the setpoint selected.

The test period revealed that the COD values varied too little to justify an integration of this in the control strategy. The maximum value measured was 74 mg COD/l, the minimum was 50 mg COD/l and the average value was 60 mg COD/l. However, the testing period was quite short compared to the variations in the COD concentration. Looking at a larger data amount for the COD concentration in the effluent reveals that the COD concentration in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers does change, however over months and years, not on a daily or weekly basis. The changes in ozone between these minimum and maximum values would be dosing 12 mgO₃/l at the lowest and 17 mgO₃/l at the highest. The resources that would need to be used for programming, integration and maintenance would be too high compared to the energy savings. It was decided to go forward with a fixed dosage in the ozonation process. This is a simple control strategy that does not require any measurement tools, but also has a greater risk of over- and under-dosing in case of changes in the effluent water quality from the activated sludge plant.

Experience with online COD measuring for control of the ozone dose

The COD sensor from WTW was installed at the effluent from the secondary clarifier in a well with continuous through flow as the water continues onto tertiary treatment. The installation at Kalundborg WWTP is seen in Figure 3.

The well always has a fixed water level, hence the COD sensor was hanging from the top down to the bottom of the well into the water phase. Beside the COD sensor an oxygen sensor and a suspended solid sensor is placed in the well

Figure 3: Placement of the online COD sensor at Kalundborg WWTP.

The COD sensor measured directly in the stream from the secondary clarifiers, without any pre-filtration of the water. The sensors have their own ultrasonic cleaning system to prevent scaling on the sensor. A picture of the sensor is seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Used sensor for online COD measurements.

The sensor was tested over the course of 47 days, with 32 laboratory double measurements of COD, to find the best calibration for the sensor. After the first eight days the sensor was calibrated (indicated at the figure with a red line), and after that no further calibration was done. The results of the lab measurements and the corresponding sensor value can be found in the figure below. Here it can be found that the values from laboratory analysis and the sensor measured value correspond with a reasonable fit. The average difference measured by the sensor and the laboratory value was 1.9 mg COD/L (Figure 5). The sensor was only cleaned once on 15/10, which did not affect the measured values.

In general, the specific type of sensor must be adapted to the local conditions and the local COD matrix at the specific WWTP. Large variations within the COD matrix at a plant can cause instability for the sensor type.

Figure 5: Correlation between laboratory and online COD measurements.

Under normal conditions, the operational staff observes high degrees of growth on the online suspended solids sensors in the effluent. Especially species of *Vorticella* (Figure 6) grow on the sensors installed in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers at Kalundborg WWTP. Under normal conditions, an online mixed liquor suspended solids sensor installed in the effluent will clog with *Vorticella* growth after a few hours of operation. This was, however, not the case in relation to the online COD sensor. It is unknown if this was due to specific process conditions during the time of operation, or if it was due to the optimized ultrasonic cleaning system of the sensor. The cleaning frequency was set to the standard settings from the contractor, which was 1 cleaning/minute.

Figure 6: *Vorticella* in activated sludge flocks.

Overall, the experience with the sensor was positive, but due to cost and at the time some uncertainties about the length of the ozonation plant operation, this control strategy was not further developed.

Monitoring and removal of relevant APIs

The catchment area for Kalundborg WWTP does not contain any hospitals. However, several API species are measured in the WWTP influent, which confirms that API removal is very relevant at all WWTPs, with or without the direct discharge of hospital wastewater.

API removal was measured on several occasions and under different ozonation conditions, outlined below:

1. As a baseline study conducted in 2016 by DHI group: samples were taken from the influent streams and the effluent from the secondary clarifiers
2. In January 2019, samples were taken from the effluent of the secondary clarifiers and the effluent of the ozone plant
3. In February 2019, a dose-response test was conducted to identify correlations between API elimination and ozone dosage
4. In December 2019, samples were taken at all influent streams, at internal streams such as reject water and waste activated sludge, at the effluent of the secondary clarifiers, at the effluent of the ozone plant, and at the effluent of the MBBR plant

Results from the baseline study conducted in 2016 by DHI has not been included into this report. This is due to the fact that the sampling was done several years ago, hence it is possibly no longer valid. Furthermore, the sampling was done as a mixed sample collected over several weeks, which cannot be compared to the flow- and time-proportional samples collected over the following three sampling campaigns.

Figure 7 depicts the API concentrations in the effluent of the secondary clarifiers. Many of the concentrations in the effluent of the secondary clarifiers are below marine PNEC values or LOQ, which is not attributed to a higher degree of conversion in the activated sludge plant or adsorption onto the waste activated sludge. The municipal wastewater, containing the majority of the APIs directed to Kalundborg WWTP, is diluted with industrial wastewater from biotech industries, which also dilutes the API concentrations. The section about ecotoxicity and the risk assessment, respectively, will address the matter in more detail.

Figure 7: Concentrations of selected APIs in the effluent of the secondary clarifiers at Kalundborg WWTP.

API removal in January 2019

The data campaign in January 2019 focused on the removal efficiency of the tertiary treatment at Kalundborg WWTP. The red dots in Figure 8 illustrate the sampling locations in the schematic flow diagram of Kalundborg WWTP. All samples were time proportional samples collected over a period of 24 hours.

Figure 8: Collection of samples for API campaign in January 2019. Sampling points are highlighted with red dots.

Data from the sampling campaign are provided in SI-Table 1. The removal efficiency of APIs during ozonation is seen in Figure 9. Eight of 17 species had a removal efficiency higher than 90 % despite the low ozone dose of 0.56 mg O₃/mg DOC.

Figure 9: Removal of APIs in the ozonation stage in January 2019. Specific ozone dose was 0.56 mg O₃/mg DOC (where no graph is shown data is not available). Removal was set to 100% if API at the ozonation effluent was below LOQ.

Dose-response test for API removal

In February 2019, a series of dose-response tests were carried out over two days. The purpose of this was to validate the effect and changes to the wastewater characteristics at different ozone concentrations.

An estimated DOC content was calculated based on the COD content of the wastewater during the test, but the actual DOC content of the wastewater was slightly lower, which resulted in a change in the actual specific dosage tested in the dose-response test. Data from the test are provided in the appendix (SI-Table 2).

Several parameters were evaluated during the dose-response test, including COD, DOC, TN, NH₄, NO₂, NO₃, bromide, bromate, UVA₂₅₄, fluorescence (fDOM), and API concentrations. Most species do not change significantly during the ozone treatment. Especially the nitrogen species are very stable (SI-Figure 1). However, both UVA₂₅₄ and fluorescence changed with the ozone as presented in Figure 10. A decrease is seen for both parameters as ozone preferably attacks aromatic structures (aromatic rings or unsaturated double/triple carbon bonds) that are closely linked to these parameters.

Figure 10: Impact of ozonation on UVA₂₅₄ (top) and fluorescence (fDOM, bottom), respectively, in relation to the specific ozone dose.

Due to uncertainties of the hydraulic retention time between the inlet and the outlet measurement points of the ozonation plant, a time of one hour was chosen to ensure a complete hydraulic retention time cycle.

In the dose-response test, there was no apparent changes in the nitrogen content (data shown in the appendix). TN, NH₄ and NO₃ did not change from the inlet to the outlet of the ozonation plant. The NO₂ was only measured in the inlet of the ozonation plant, in order to correct the specific ozone dose for the ozone consumption by nitrite. As the NO₂-N content had an average concentration of 0.03 mg/L, with a maximum of 0.06 mg/L, taking the NO₂ content into account when considering the ozone dosage was not found to be relevant. DOC was measured at the inlet of the ozonation

plant, as it only has relevance as a control parameter. There was an average concentration of 16.7 mg/l of DOC, with a minimum and maximum of 15 and 17 mg/L.

The dissolved COD content in the inlet and outlet was analysed in all samples, and results are shown in Figure 11. The COD content of the wastewater was not inversely linearly related to increasing ozone dosage, although a decrease in the dissolved COD concentration can be seen with increasing specific ozone dose. However, the uncertainty of the method must be considered, resulting in the fact that the difference between influent and effluent at specific ozone doses $> 1 \text{ mgO}_3/\text{mgDOC}$ is approximately 5-7%. Since only COD in the influent and effluent was measured, a full mass balance cannot be conducted. However, the graph does show that some COD is oxidized in the ozone plant and that amount is increasing with increasing ozone dose.

Figure 11: Impact of ozonation on dissolved COD concentration in relation to the specific ozone dose.

Dose-response tests on API removal were also conducted to determine optimal conditions for API removal at Kalundborg WWTP for which the results are shown in Figure 12. As can be seen in the figure, the setpoint for realistic full-scale operation is $0.8 \text{ mg O}_3/\text{mg DOC}$. At this setpoint a removal efficiency between 40-100 % can be seen, depending on the API in question.

Several compounds, such as sulfamethizole, sulfamethoxazole, losartan, diclofenac, citalopram and carbamazepine are not depicted at the figure. This is due to the fact that removal below LOQ was seen at the lowest specific ozone dose. Hence 100 % removal at $0.52 \text{ mg O}_3/\text{mg DOC}$ is assumed. Also, tramadol follows a similar pattern, with only a slightly lower removal efficiency at an ozone dose of $0.52 \text{ mg O}_3/\text{mg DOC}$.

The lowest removal efficiencies are seen for gabapentin, oxazepam and irbesartan. In order to obtain an average removal of 80 % for the 3 species, the relative ozone dose should be $1.3 \text{ mg O}_3/\text{mg DOC}$. The results in Figure 12 show good coherence with the results obtained in the data campaign from January 2019.

Figure 12: Relative API removal in respect to the specific ozone dose. Removal was set to 100% if API at the ozonation effluent was below LOQ.

Mass balances for APIs based on data from sampling campaign in December 2019

In December 2019 an extensive campaign to monitor APIs, bromide/bromate and standard wastewater parameters was conducted at Kalundborg WWTP. During one week, samples from internal as well as external streams were collected. Sampling points are denoted by red dots in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Sample collection for extensive sampling program in December 2019. Sampling points are highlighted with red dots.

Figure 13 only shows a joined influent to Kalundborg WWTP. However, the influent is separated into 3 streams before they are joined in the inlet pumping station. The 3 streams consist of the following:

1. Sanitary wastewater from the city and smaller industries
2. Wastewater from the biotech industries
3. Wastewater from the power plant

All three streams have been included in the sampling program. Looking at the data, API species directed to Kalundborg WWTP comes from the sanitary wastewater sewage line. In the wastewater from the power plant iohexol, gabapentin, venlafaxine and diclofenac were present in concentrations above the LOQ. In the stream from the biotech industries, benzotriazole was present in much higher concentrations compared to the city and power plant, and was the only API above the LOQ.

The results from the campaign are shown in Figure 14. The reduction is calculated as the following:

1. Reduction in the activated sludge plant is the influent concentration related to the concentration in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers
2. Reduction in the tertiary treatment is the influent concentration to the ozone plant (effluent from the secondary clarifiers) and the effluent from the ozone plant
3. Reduction in the MBBR plant is the influent to the MBBR plant (effluent from the ozone plant) related to the effluent from the MBBR plant

Figure 14: Overall API elimination at WWTP with respect to the elimination at the different treatment stages (CAS, Ozone and MBBR). Results from sampling campaigns in December 2019 (n = 3 or n = 2 if marked with *).

The figure above does not contain the following data from the data campaign:

1. API species that were below limit of quantification in the influent to the WWTP (sotalol, propranolol, azithromycin, ciprofloxacin, diatrizoic acid, candesartan, iopromide, valsartan and ibuprofen)
2. API species that were below limit of quantification after the CAS, but with an influent concentration greater than 5 times limit of quantification (atenolol, iohexol, sulfadiazine, sulfamethoxazole, roxithromycin, mycophenolic acid and irbesartan)
3. API species that were below limit of quantification after the ozone treatment, but with an influent concentration greater than 5 times the limit of quantification (oxazepam)

API species below limit of quantification after the CAS might be below the limit either do to aerobic/anoxic conversion in the CAS or due to dilution with wastewater from the biotech industries. Data has shown that the wastewater from the biotech industries generally has concentration below LOQ for most API's, thus the flow contributes to a certain degree of dilution.

Some of the X-ray-contrast media (e.g. iohexol, iopamidol,i) are biologically degraded by 80% – 90, which is unusual. Only iomeprol was detected in the previous campaigns (DHI 2016, September 2018 and January 2019). During the DHI campaign in 2016, a removal efficiency of 93.9 % was obtained in

the activated sludge plant for iomeprol. In the September 2018 campaign, a removal efficiency of 0 % in the ozone plant was obtained, and during the January 2019 campaign, the concentration in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers was below LOQ. Hence the data for this specific type of compounds varies a lot and it is difficult to conclude removal patterns based on the data. However, some degree of dilution must be expected due to the wastewater from the biotech industries.

Benzotriazole seems to be high in the wastewater from the biotech industries, which seems logical, as instead of dilution, an increase is seen in WWTP influent. Very low concentrations of iomeprol, venlafaxine, citalopram, roxithromycin and DCF-OH are seen in the wastewater from the biotech industries. The concentrations of these compounds are all below 0.05 µg/l, thus they are in a low range compared to the wastewater from the city. The fact that they are present could be explained by the fact that some of the sanitary wastewater might be directed to local WWTP at the biotech industries (connections that are wrongly connected to the industrial WWTP instead of the municipal sewage system). The only species that are strongly represented in the wastewater from the biotech industries are bromide and benzotriazole, which makes sense when taking the nature of the industry into consideration.

Reduction of carbamazepine and diclofenac during ozonation is very low and does not correlate with either literature or the rest of the data sets. Carbamazepine was only measured during the campaign in January 2019, however during the campaign a removal of 100 % in the ozone plant was obtained. Diclofenac was measured during all campaigns and removals of 68 % in September 2018 and 100 % in January 2019 were obtained.

Ozonation by-products

Several by products can be formed during ozonation, however attentive project and report delimits the by-products to bromate and transformation products in relation to oxidation of API's.

Bromate

Bromate is a known ozonation by-product of bromide. Bromide occurs in varying concentrations in most bodies of water, although it is mostly present in high concentrations in saltwater¹. Due to its high concentration in saltwater, it is especially relevant to investigate bromate formation in wastewater treatment plants geographically close to coastal areas, such as Kalundborg WWTP.

Dose-response experiments

During February 2019, dose-response experiments for bromate formation were conducted at Kalundborg WWTP. The bromate concentration was analysed in the influent wastewater to the ozonation plant as well as in the effluent. The influent and effluent concentrations from the ozonation plant can be found in the appendix (SI-Table 3).

The correlation between the ozone doses and the bromate concentration can be seen from Figure 15. For that data set, which was obtained during a relatively constant bromide concentration in the influent to the ozone plant, the bromate formation is linear ($R^2 = 0.9924$ and $R^2 = 0.9899$). It must be considered that the bromide concentration in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers are high compared to measurements conducted in December 2019. The data from December 2019 shows a bromide concentration on average of 1.9 mg BrO₃/l, against an average concentration of 2.8 mg BrO₃/l during the testing in February 2019.

Figure 15: Bromate formation in respect to the specific ozone dose.

The load in kg BrO₃/d can be calculated from the flow and corresponds to approximately 45 kg BrO₃/d during the samples taken in February 2019, whereas the load calculated in December 2019 corresponds to 40 kg BrO₃/d. In general, the load is very similar and within the variations that can be expected due to rain and infiltration in the sewage network. Data from the influent to Kalundborg WWTP shows that during the February campaign no rain occurred, whereas heavy rainfall occurred during the December campaign.

¹ A general assumption is 65 mg Br⁻/l in saltwater

Since the bromate formation is, among others, a consequence of the bromide concentration and not load (in combination with the ozone dosage), it must be considered that the bromate formation during lower bromide concentration will be lower than the estimated 0.1 mg BrO₃/l at a specific ozone dose of 0.8 mg O₃/mg DOC. Hence the data displayed in the figure is an expression of the worst-case scenario in relation to bromate formation.

There are few references on acceptable bromate concentrations to marine environments. However, Switzerland operates with a concentration of 50 µg/l in water bodies². The risk assessment conducted by DHI (see appendix, in Danish) initially proposed a marine PNEC value for bromate at 1.1 µg/l. However, additional experiments conducted with *Acartia tonsa* suggested that the marine PNEC value could be increased to 11 µg/l (data from tests are enclosed in the appendix, in Danish). The bromate PNEC concentration is generally very low due to high uncertainty in the data and lack of data regarding the toxicity of bromate to marine environments.

Bromide source tracking in the catchment area

Data from the operation of the ozone plant during March to April 2019 shows that the bromate formation occurs during the ozonation process. Table 2 below shows the data from that period. As can be seen from the table, the data varies and there is no clear correlation between influent bromide concentration, the DOC setpoint and the bromate concentration in the effluent from the ozonation plant.

Table 2: Bromate measurements from the full-scale operation during March and April 2019 (bromate measured on 23/3 seems very low and does not correspond with literature data). * indicates high influent flows due to rain on these dates.

Date	Influent bromide (mg/l)	Effluent bromate (mg/l)	Specific ozone dose (mg O ₃ /mg DOC)
23/03/2019	2.68	<0.015	0.80
27/03/2019	2.17	0.144	0.75
02/04/2019	2.54	0.195	1.00
05/04/2019	1.60*	0.023	0.63
09/04/2019	1.77*	0.110	0.63
26/04/2019	1.73*	0.540	0.71

Due to the limitations of the dataset above, an extensive sampling program for bromide and bromate was conducted at Kalundborg WWTP during December 2019. The aim was to supplement the data collected earlier in the project and extend the data to also consider the influent flow to the wastewater treatment plant.

Samples were collected for 7 days from selected places at the wastewater treatment plant. A layout of the sampling program is shown in Figure 13.

The influent samples were collected from four different streams:

1. The municipal wastewater which is the sanitary wastewater from the households in the city of Kalundborg and smaller industries
2. Wastewater from biotech industries in the city
3. Wastewater from a power plant based in Kalundborg
4. Old waste dump in Ubberrup, which discharges to the municipal system

The data from the four influent streams can be seen in Table 3. As can be seen from the concentrations and loadings, most of the bromide originates from the municipal wastewater and from the wastewater of the biotech industries.

² <https://www.ecotoxcentre.ch/expert-service/quality-standards/proposals-for-acute-and-chronic-quality-standards/>

Table 3: Influent bromide concentrations, December 2019.

Influent stream	Average bromide concentration (mg Br ⁻ /l)	Average bromide load (kg Br ⁻ /d)
Municipal wastewater	2.16	25
Biotech industry wastewater	1.49	16
Power plant wastewater	0.39	0.02
Ubberup waste dump	1.05	0.17

The bromide concentration in the wastewater coming from the municipal waste stream is within the high range, even for wastewater treatment plants originated in coastal areas. The high bromide concentration is a potential problem for the ozone treatment of the wastewater due to the low PNEC value for bromate in marine environments (see also section on Environmental risk assessment).

Since sea water contains an average of 65 mg Br⁻/l, saltwater intrusion in the catchment area could with reason be suspected to be the origin of the high bromide concentration. If it is assumed that the entire bromide source for the municipal stream origins from saltwater intrusion, it would require about 384 m³/d. This amount would correspond to about 3,3 % of the overall wastewater treated per day. However, even though the source of bromide for the municipal wastewater could be identified, the bromide load from the biotech industries would still result in a concentration of approximately 1 mg Br⁻/l in the effluent wastewater, which is too high for ozonation.

In order to rule out the water resources as the source of saltwater, all water resources were tested for bromide. The water works of Diegtvad treats water from its own well but mixes the water with water extracted from Vn/Marke. Vn/Marke consist of eight different wells, some private, some belonging to the neighbour utility. The industries are supplied by Diegtvad water works and Tissø water. An overview of the bromide concentrations in the water supply for the catchment area is seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Bromide concentrations in the water resources in the catchment area for Kalundborg WWTP.

Water resource	Origin	Bromide concentration (mg Br ⁻ /l)	Extraction (m ³ /year)	Bromide loading to catchment area (kg Br ⁻ /d)
Groundwater	Brandsbjerg water works	0.35	126,889	0.12
Groundwater	Hjorthøj water works	0.17	144,032	0.07
Groundwater	Trøjelykke water works	0.33	27,866	0.03
Groundwater	Diegtvad water works	0.18	1,247,000	0.61
Groundwater	Vn/Marke joined water works	0.13	1,309,000	0.47
Groundwater	Gørløv water works	0.26	380,000	0.27
Surface water (raw)	Tissø	0.09	2,624,000	0.62
Surface water (treated)	Tissø 2	0.32	1,278,000	1.12
Backflush treated surface water	Tissø 2	0.20	NA	NA

The raw surface water and treated surface water differs quite a lot in bromide concentration. The intake from the catchment area is the same for both, hence variations in the lake cannot explain the difference between the two samples. Most likely this can be explained by an analytical error.

The total average daily load from the water resources is 3.3 kg Br⁻/d, corresponding to 8.5 % of the total bromide load to Kalundborg municipal WWTP.

The bromide from the biotech industries thus must originate from one of two sources:

1. Raw materials used in the production, besides the water supply, or
2. Infiltration to the pipeline transporting the wastewater from the industries to Kalundborg municipal WWTP

From the biotech companies which have a separate discharge to the WWTP it has been stated that a biocide is used in the cooling towers on site. This could be responsible for emissions of approximately 892 kg Br⁻/year, corresponding to 2.5 kg Br⁻/d or approximately 0.24 mg Br⁻/l. Furthermore, salts used in the production could be responsible for additional bromide concentrations. This is being investigated further.

To rule out saltwater intrusion to the wastewater pipeline from the biotech industries, chloride measurements have been taken at each end of the pipeline directing the wastewater from the biotech industries to Kalundborg WWTP. The chloride concentration is used as an indicator for saltwater infiltration to the pipe. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Chloride concentration in each of the pipeline from the biotech industries.

Sampling point	Sampling type	Sampling date	Chloride concentration (mg/l)	Estimated amount of infiltration
Biotech Industries	Flow proportional sampling	14.02.2020	140	73 %
Kalundborg WWTP	Flow proportional sampling	14.02.2020	105	55 %

Due to the nature of the analysis (HACH test kit) it is fair to assume that the concentration in both ends of the pipe is similar, as is the amount of infiltration. From the values in Table 5, it stands to reason that the bromide sources to Kalundborg WWTP do not come from infiltration of saltwater into the pipeline transporting the wastewater from the biotech industries to the WWTP.

The bromide from the municipal wastewater can originate from one of the following sources:

1. Infiltration into the network system, or
2. Other companies discharging wastewater containing bromide to the WWTP

Together with the local municipality which issues the discharge permits to all local industries, potential bromide sources have been investigated. However, only one potential source from a biocide in a cooling tower was identified, although the biocide had been changed several years ago and the current bromide concentration in the effluent from the industry was below the detection limit.

Therefore, a campaign in the catchment area was also initiated in order to track possible saltwater infiltration to the sewage network (Figure 16). Time proportional samplers equipped for sampling every hour were located at three positions in the catchment. Furthermore, grab samples were collected at one position.

Figure 16: Sample collection in the catchment area to Kalundborg WWTP.

Time proportional samplers were chosen to collect one sample/hour over 24 hours. By doing so the saltwater infiltration can be followed during the day when the pipe is more or less full. The water from the harbor is a purely rainwater pipe system, however the system is connected to the wastewater treatment plant, thus there might be saltwater in this part due to the location close to the water.

Initial testing shows that a large amount of infiltration of seawater takes place in the pipe system along the coastline. Data from the sampler at Hervigsgade/Vestre Havnevej and from Sydhavnsvej/ Dokhavnsvej is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 17: Chloride sampling at a sampling point in the catchment area near the seaside.

Figure 18: Chloride sampling at a sampling point at the other end of the catchment area away from the seaside.

Samples that shows zero were attributed to an error on the automatic sampler when no samples were sucked into the sampler. This was due to a too low filling in the pipe. Hence, the concentration is not 0 mg/l. The average concentration at Figure 17 is 2.000 mg Cl⁻/l and corresponds to a bromide concentration of 7 mg Br⁻/l, whereas the average concentration at Figure 18 is 97 mg Cl⁻/l and corresponds to a bromide concentration of 0.3 mg Br⁻/l.

Further investigations of the upper catchment area have shown that the pipe running along the coastline in Figure 16 has a large degree of infiltration and this pipe will be renovated. The investigations have also shown that during high water level in Kalundborg bay the saltwater runs backwards into the pipe system because the back flow prevention is not working properly. This will also be corrected and replaced where demanded.

Transformation products

It is well known that the micropollutants are transformed into other compounds during ozonation. For example, tertiary amines (e.g. tramadol, venlafaxine, erythromycin, etc.) react with ozone and are transformed into their respective *N*-oxides. The concentrations of tramadol *N*-oxide and venlafaxine *N*-oxide in the inflow for ozonation were below LOQ. However, after ozonation, their concentrations were greater than LOQ and their concentrations in the outlet of ozonation plant in dependence with specific ozone dose are shown in Figure 19. The concentration of *N*-oxides indeed increases after ozonation. Gradual decrease in concentration is seen in the graph for both *N*-oxides when specific ozone dose increased further from 0.6 mg O₃/mg DOC. As the specific ozone doses below 0.5 mg O₃/mg DOC were not tested, the depiction of formation and removal of these *N*-oxides were not clear. Nevertheless, the complete picture of formation and removal of these *N*-oxides (in other plants) were published in Kharel et al. (2020) and in CWPharma report 3.3 (Stapf et al., 2020).

Figure 19: Concentration of N-oxides of tramadol and venlafaxine in the effluent of the ozonation plant at different specific ozone doses.

Optimization of MBBR operation

The MBBR plant has a volume of 1,200 m³ and is designed for a capacity of 1,200 m³/h. This corresponds approximately to half the design flow of the entire wastewater treatment plant, hence the remaining flow during peak hours will be directed around the tertiary treatment, mixed with the effluent from the tertiary treatment and then directed into the plant. The plant consists of 4 chambers, which all have approximately 25 % carrier elements (volume-wise). The carrier elements are AnoxKaldness K1 types with a surface area of 600 m²/m³. An overview of the plant is seen in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Schematic drawing of the MBBR plant at Kalundborg. The plant consists of four chambers, of which the first two chambers have mixing and aeration, and the last two only have mixing installed.

The plant can be fed either with the effluent from the ozone plant or the effluent from the secondary clarifiers. This installation was constructed to continue feeding the plant in periods during which the ozone plant was not operational.

Under normal operational conditions only the joined effluent from the MBBR plant and the secondary clarifiers is measured. However, in periods with a higher frequency of sampling, both the influent and effluent of the MBBR were sampled. Two campaigns were conducted in relation for CWPharma:

1. A period from 30/5-2017 to 23/11-2017, during which the ozone plant was not in operation;
2. A period from 23/3-2019 to 26/4-2019 with few measurements, during which the ozone plant was operating at a specific ozone dose of 0.76 mg DOC/mg COD
3. A period from 11/12-2019 to 17/12-2019, during which the ozone plant was operating at a specific ozone dose of 0.8 mg DOC/mg COD

Data from the influent and effluent of the MBBR plant can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6: Average concentrations of different water quality parameters measured at the influent and effluent of the MBBR plant with time proportional samples.

Sampling point	Sampling campaign	COD (mg/l)	TN (mg/l)	NH ₄ (mg/l)	NO ₃ (mg/l)	TP (mg/l)	PO ₄ (mg/l)
MBBR influent	Year 2017	61.4	6.2	0.18	1.8	0.65	-
MBBR effluent	Year 2017	59.2	6.2	0.03	1.9	0.65	-
MBBR influent	March 2019	44.1	5.1	0.30	1.4	-	-
MBBR effluent	March 2019	42.4	5.2	0.26	1.5	-	-
MBBR influent	December 2019	37.2	5.94	0.12	3.32	0.32	0.25
MBBR effluent	December 2019	37.5	5.91	0.07	3.39	0.34	0.24

In general, the following can be concluded from the two data sets:

1. The COD concentration in the influent to the MBBR plant has decreased over time. This could be due to change in the activation process, the COD conversion at the biotech industries wastewater treatment plant that has changed the composition of the COD or an increase in the sludge age at Kalundborg WWTP.
2. The nitrogen species has also changed between the data sets. In the data from the 2017 campaign a larger part of the nitrogen is in a form not measured, neither as ammonia nor as nitrate. This could be due to a higher degree of inert nitrogen bound to the higher amount of inert COD or due to higher amounts of SS in the influent from the secondary clarifiers.
3. The TN and TP at the influent and effluent of the MBBR is very similar in the campaigns.
4. In all campaigns the ammonia in the effluent from the MBBR is lower than the influent, this makes sense since the first two chambers of the MBBR plant are heavily aerated and ammonia should be oxidised to nitrate or incorporated into biomass.
5. Although the ozone plant was running during the two campaigns in 2019, it does not seem to have an effect on the COD degradation in the MBBR plant.

Not a great deal of conversion is seen in any parameter (COD, nitrogen or phosphorus). This is expected due to the low amount of biomass on the carrier elements. The lack of biomass is also expected due to the low degree of substrate that the MBBR plant receives. In relation to the COD, most of the COD will not be biodegradable, and the part of the COD that is not oxidized during ozonation will not be absorbed onto the biomass either. With regards to nitrogen, the COD/TN ratio was between 6-10, depending on the campaign. This should, in theory, be sufficient for denitrification and for AOB and NOB to grow in the biomass. However, since the COD is unavailable for biological conversion and the plant is so heavily aerated, the oxygen is carried through the plant from the aerobic chambers to the anoxic chambers and therefore no denitrification will take place. Finally, the COD/TP ratio > 100 presents difficult conditions for sustaining a continuous biomass since the amount of the phosphorous is simply too low.

Looking at the COD speciation in the campaigns in 2019, the tendencies were quite different. In the dataset from March, the data showed that an increasing amount of COD was converted in the MBBR plant, until a level of 30-40 mg COD/l was reached in the effluent from the MBBR plant. In the data from December 2019, the trend did not continue, despite the fact that the ozone plant had been running continuously between the sampling campaigns. Both campaigns were operated with the same ozone setpoint, but in the December campaign it is clear that an average of 17 % COD removal is obtained in the ozone plant, which is a positive side effect of the API reduction (Figure 21).

Figure 21: COD concentration at the influent and effluent of the ozonation and the effluent of the MBBR in March 2019 (top) and in December 2019 (bottom), respectively.

In general, the COD concentration in the joined effluent decreased over time. The data from the joined effluent at Kalundborg WWTP at the year 2017 is shown in Figure 22. In comparison, COD concentration decreased from almost 60 mg/l in the year 2017 to around 50 mg/l in the end of 2019. During the time were the tertiary treatment was operated, both samples from the effluent of the MBBR plant as well as the joined effluent were analysed.

Figure 22: COD concentrations in the joined effluent from Kalundborg WWTP and the effluent of the MBBR plant during 2017.

Since most of the water was treated in the tertiary treatment, there are few data points where the water was directed around the tertiary treatment and directly into the recipient of the secondary clarifiers. However, it is not sufficient to state any conclusions based on the data. The COD concentration in the two streams is more or less similar, hence it cannot be concluded that the effluent from the MBBR plant dilutes the effluent from the secondary clarifiers in regards to COD.

Lab scale experiment for kinetic clarification (conducted by AU)

Previous studies have shown that manipulating the loading of easily degradable carbon into an MBBR can lead to enhanced or faster degradation of some pharmaceuticals (Casas et al., 2015; Tang et al., 2017).

Two laboratory scale experiments were carried out to assess the effect of this manipulation on MBBRs ability to remove pharmaceuticals.

The principle behind the experiments was the frequency between feast (high COD/BOD load) and famine (low COD/no BOD load) periods. Both experiments were designed to test the same 12 different frequencies.

Experiment 1

The reactors in experiment 1 used effluent wastewater as the famine condition and raw wastewater as the feast condition (approximately 790 mg COD/L). The water was collected from Bjergmarken wastewater treatment plant in Roskilde. The carriers were Z carriers (Annox Kaldnes).

Experiment 2

The reactors in experiment 2 used secondary effluent as the famine condition, and secondary wastewater mixed with ethanol as BOD source (approximately 230 mg COD/L) as the feast condition. The water was collected from Kalundborg treatment plant. The carriers were K₁ carriers from the first chamber of the Kalundborg full-scale MBBR plant.

Both experiments 1 and 2 had four 1-L reactors available. The 12 tested feast-famine frequencies were therefore run in three blocks of four treatments each. The last block of experiment 2 was finished in June 2020.

Setup:

Four 1-L reactors were set up as flow-through systems, supplied with either feast or famine type water with a hydraulic retention time of approximately four hours. The reactors were constantly aerated to saturation. The 12 different treatment frequencies are outlined in Table 7: Tested frequencies between feast (raw wastewater or effluent wastewater spiked with ethanol) and famine (effluent wastewater) conditions. Treatment name reflects the number of famine days; "C" is for constant. The feast-famine cycle for each reactor was repeated for two months. One treatment (Treatment C) was kept running constantly on famine conditions, resembling a polishing reactor without any additional COD added. The remaining treatments (Treatments 2-12) were running on cycles of two days feast followed by 2-12 days of famine, for two months. Differences and similarities between experiment 1 and 2 are outlined in Table 7.

Experiment 1: A biofilm were established over 4 months on the new Z400 carriers. The carriers were then divided into the four reactors. The reactors were run in three blocks, first on treatment 4, 5, 6 and 7. The reactors and carriers were then reused for treatment 2, 3, 8 and 9, and then again for treatment 1, 10, 11 and 12. Each block of treatments lasted two months. After each block, a batch incubation was carried out: the carriers were transferred to flasks with effluent wastewater spiked with pharmaceuticals (10 µg/L), to determine the degradation kinetics of pharmaceuticals. After the last block, two treatments from block 1 (treatment 4 and 6) were repeated. For the repetition of treatment 6, an additional batch incubation using effluent wastewater spiked with ozonation transformation products (5 µg/L) was carried out, to assess the potential of MBBR to remove these.

Experiment 2: K₁ carriers with an established biofilm were taken from the first chamber of the full scale MBBR plant and divided into the four reactors. The reactors were run in three blocks. After each block, a batch incubation was carried out in the same matter as above. After each block, the carriers were exchanged with fresh carriers from the full scale MBBR plant.

Table 7: Tested frequencies between feast (raw wastewater or effluent wastewater spiked with ethanol) and famine (effluent wastewater) conditions. Treatment name reflects the number of famine days; “C” is for constant. The feast-famine cycle for each reactor was repeated for two months.

Treatment ID	Feast (days)	Famine (days)	Number of cycles
2	2	2	15
3	2	3	12
4	2	4	10
5	2	5	9
6	2	6	8
7	2	7	7
8	2	8	6
9	2	9	5
10	2	10	5
11	2	11	5
12	2	12	4
C	0	Constant	1

Table 8: Operational parameters for the reactors in experiments 1 and 2.

Parameter	Experiment 1	Experiment 2
Volume	1 l	1 l
Feast	Raw wastewater (790 ± 277 mg COD L ⁻¹)	Effluent wastewater with ethanol (280 ± 10 mg COD L ⁻¹)
Famine	Effluent wastewater (36 ± 10 mg COD L ⁻¹)	Effluent wastewater (47 ± 10 mg COD L ⁻¹)
Water source	Bjergmarken	Kalundborg
Hydraulic residence time	4 h	4 h
Carrier type	Z400	K1
Reuse of carriers	Yes	No

The degradation of the individual pharmaceuticals during the 12 different treatments was fitted with a single first-order (SFO) kinetics equation (Equation 1), with the corresponding half-life in hours (Equation 2). The derived degradation rate constants (K-values) from the single first-order fit were then plotted for each treatment, as seen in Figure 23.

$$\text{single first-order (SFO)} \quad C = C_0 e^{-K*t} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$\text{Half-life} \quad DT_{50} = \frac{\ln(2)}{K} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

In the above equations, C is the measured concentration (µg L⁻¹) at time t (h), C₀ is the initial concentration (µg L⁻¹) at time 0 (h), and K (h⁻¹) is the reaction rate constant from the SFO fit.

Biomass

The amount of biomass on the Z₄₀₀ carriers from experiment 1 and the K₁ carriers from experiment 2 were measured by difference weighing. Fresh carriers were transferred from the reactors to an oven (105°C) overnight and weighed. The biomass was washed off using hydrochloric acid and water in an ultrasound bath, dried in the oven again and subsequently weighed. The amount of biomass was calculated as the difference in weight.

The amount of biomass on the Z₄₀₀ carriers used in experiment 1 did not show significant differences between the different treatments, while the K₁ carriers had a factor 10 higher amount of biomass than the K₁ carriers from the full-scale plant (Figure 23). Furthermore, the amount of biomass per carrier were much higher for the K₁ lab carriers (≈ 70 mg/carrier) than the Z₄₀₀ carriers (2-5 mg/carrier). This is due to the geometry of the carriers, as the Z₄₀₀ carrier is designed to have a thin biofilm on the surface, while the inner surfaces and cavities of the K₁ carriers can accumulate higher amounts of biomass.

Figure 23: Amount of biomass per carrier for the Z₄₀₀ carriers used in Roskilde (left) and the K₁ carriers used in Kalundborg (right). The dotted lines represent the constant famine condition in the left graph, while in the right graph, it represents the amount of biomass in the full scale MBBR.

Kinetic results – experiment 1

The K-values for the pharmaceuticals show different patterns and have different optimal numbers of famine days. Roughly, the pharmaceuticals could be divided into four groups. Group 1: The highest K-values were found for treatments with 9 and 10 days of famine. This group, exemplified by diclofenac in Figure 24, contains five compounds: diclofenac, iopromide, iohexol, gabapentin and sulfamethizole.

Group 2: The K values were first increasing, then decreasing, with the highest K-values found at the treatment with 6 days famine. This group is exemplified by sulfamethoxazole (Figure 24), and contains sulfamethoxazole, sulfadiazine, phenazone, benzotriazole and tramadol.

Group 3: Two peaks were seen for the K-values, giving the highest K-values at 4 and 9/10 days of famine. Exemplified by metoprolol (Figure 24), the group contains metoprolol, propranolol, sotalol, trimethoprim and mycophenolic acid.

Group 4: The K-values showed in some cases some differences between the treatments, but no clear optimum or trend was detected. This group, exemplified by candesartan (Figure 24), contains candesartan, olmesartan, irbesartan, eprosartan, valsartan, venlafaxine, ibuprofen, diatrizoic acid and atenolol.

The feast famine optima proved to be compound specific. It is therefore difficult to choose a configuration of MBBR systems which will result in a higher removal for all compounds. A configuration should therefore be based on a prioritizing of compounds. Alternatively, several MBBR reactors in a train could be configured in different ways, thus enhancing the degradation for more groups of pharmaceuticals. However, several MBBRs in series will increase HRT and impact the cost. The differences in K-values for the different treatments were largest for the slowly degrading

compounds, as sulfamethoxazole, with a factor 8 difference between the lowest and highest K-value. The half-life for sulfamethoxazole was more than 1000 hours for the treatment constantly fed with effluent water, and 143 hours for the treatment with 6-day famine-periods. For diclofenac, there was a factor 4 increase from the lowest (at 12 days famine-periods) to the highest (at 9 days famine-periods) K values. This corresponded to a change from 296 to 75 hours for the half-life. For the fast degrading compounds such as metoprolol, the change was more subtle, with a factor 2.5 between the treatment with 7- and 4-days famine, equivalent to a half-life change from 8 to 3 hours. For candesartan, the largest difference in K-values was between the treatments with 11 and 12 days, with a factor 6 difference, equivalent to a half-life of 3 hours for 11 days famine, and half an hour for 12 days famine.

Figure 24: Single first order degradation rate constants (left y-axis, K (h^{-1})) and corresponding half-lives (right y-axis, DT_{50} (h)) plotted for the 12 different treatments (2-12 days of famine (effluent water)). The dotted line represents the constant famine conditions. Dark green: K-values from the first three blocks in experiment 1. Light green: Repetition of two treatments from block 1.

The biomass normalized K-values for experiment 1 are shown in the right side of Figure 25. As there were no significant differences between the amount of biomass (Figure 23) for the different treatments, the biomass normalized K-values show the same pattern as the non-normalized K-values.

Kinetic results - experiment 2

Due to the few data points in experiment 2, it is not possible to conclude any definite patterns or trends in K-values. However, as seen from the left side of Figure 25, the four treatments (5, 6, 7 and 8 days of famine) have higher K-values than obtained from the full scale plant (dotted line, constant famine, Figure 25). The amount of biomass on the carriers was 10 times higher on the four lab reactors (5, 6, 7 and 8 days of famine) than in the full-scale reactors (Figure 23). Thus, when normalizing the K-values to the amount of biomass, the K_{bio} -values for the full scale were higher than the lab scale biomass for metoprolol, slightly higher for sulfamethoxazole and similar for diclofenac. The similar

or higher K_{bio} -values for the full-scale plant indicate that while the overall amount of biomass increased by a factor 10, the amount of biomass active in degradation of pharmaceuticals did not. In other words, we assume a different microbial community composition in the lab reactors than in the full-scale plant. The carriers from the full-scale possibly have a higher relative amount of active degraders than the lab reactors. The full-scale plant has mainly been supplied with ozonated effluent wastewater. Thus, it is expected that such starved conditions favour microorganisms capable of degrading micropollutants. It has previously been shown for a staged MBBR system that the most efficient biofilm was found in the last reactor, receiving the lowest COD loading (Casas et al., 2015).

The application of easily degradable organic matter such as ethanol must have resulted in an increase of the general biomass.

Figure 25: Single first order degradation rate constants (K (h^{-1})) plotted for the different treatments. Left: K -values from experiment 2. Right: K -values from experiment 1 and experiment 2, normalized to the amount of biomass. The dotted lines represent constant famine conditions.

Comparison of the degradation rate constants from experiment 1 and 2 should be done with caution. The two experiments have different types of carriers, different sources of water, and different feast-conditions. Thus, it is difficult to pinpoint the reason for differences observed in the two experiments. A full comparison can be attempted when all data from experiment 2 is analysed. For now we can conclude that the biomass normalized K_{bio} -values are lower for experiment 2 than for experiment 1 as expected for a comparison of a single carbon source (ethanol) against a complex source (raw wastewater).

Removal experiment

The removal of the pharmaceuticals in the different MBBR treatments was studied by taking samples from the in- and outflow of the reactors. This was performed in the last week before batch incubation, when the reactors were running on famine (effluent). The removal of pharmaceuticals present (at concentrations five times LOQ) in the effluent wastewater is shown in Figure 26. Negative removal was observed for some compounds. This is typically due to back transformation of metabolites. As also seen from the kinetic experiments, the removal behaviour is compound-specific. The measured removal was in general the same order of magnitude as the theoretical removal, although for some treatments, deviations were observed. This was true for treatment 2 and treatment C, where the measured removal was higher than the theoretical.

Conclusions

Generally speaking, the MBBR performance can be enhanced by an adequate feeding process. The optimal feeding process were compound specific, and no single feeding strategy resulted in enhanced removal of all compounds. The measurements of APIs in flow through samples from the MBBRs were used to calculate API removal. Three APIs had removal above 80% for at least one of the feeding strategies, while an additional four APIs had removals above 50% for at least one of the feeding strategies. The degradation kinetics experiment of 13 ozonation TPs showed that MBBRs are capable of degrading four compounds with half-lives below 50 hours (DCPA $DT_{50} = 1\text{h}$, diclofenac amide $DT_{50} = 18\text{h}$, hydroxy diclofenac $DT_{50} = 21\text{h}$, BaQD $DT_{50} = 44\text{h}$), while the remaining compounds showed limited or no degradation ($DT_{50} > 50\text{h}$). At short HRT, only DCPA can be expected to be removed. The half-life times for the studied APIs range from less than an hour to more than 1000 hours, showing the vast diversity of degradability of pharmaceuticals. A boxplot of calculated half-lives over the 12 treatments in experiment 1 is shown in Figure 27. At an HRT of five hours, it can be expected that more than 50% of 10 out of the 30 APIs can be removed, as shown by the low DT_{50} in the top graph of Figure 27. Increasing the HRT to 20 hours will result in 16 APIs with removal $> 50\%$.

Figure 26: Relative removal (%) of pharmaceuticals for the 12 MBBR treatments running on famine (effluent wastewater) conditions. "C" is constant effluent water.

Figure 27: Overview of the calculated half-lives (DT_{50}) from all 12 treatments in experiment 1, shown as boxplots.

Ecotoxicity tests and by-products

During the CWPharma project, several tests with the goal of quantifying the ecotoxicity of samples were conducted and results published in the GoA3.3 report (Stapf et al., 2020). The primary goal of the tests was to evaluate if the toxicity of the wastewater changed during the advanced treatment. Therefore, samples from three sampling points were collected at Kalundborg WWTP (Figure 28).

Figure 28: Overview of sample collection for ecotoxicity test at Kalundborg WWTP. Sampling points are highlighted with red dots.

Additionally to above mentioned tests within the framework of CWPharma, further following tests were conducted:

1. Ecotoxicity test conducted by the Technical University of Denmark in order to clarify the acute toxicity of the wastewater from Kalundborg WWTP. The results are shown in the appendix (in Danish).
2. Review of chronic toxicity test conducted in CWPharma. The review was conducted by the Technical University of Denmark and is included in the appendix.

All results are discussed briefly in the following section.

Ecotoxicity test

Test included in the original CW Pharma scope

Three sampling campaigns as well as a repetition were conducted at WWTP Kalundborg to investigate the impact of ozonation and MBBR post-treatment on a broad range of ecotoxicological endpoints such as neurotoxicity, mutagenicity, genotoxicity, endocrine effects, growth and reproduction. Samples were taken at the ozonation influent as well as the effluents of the ozonation and MBBR, respectively. For all sampling campaigns an ozone dose of 12 mgO₃/L was targeted that would correspond to a specific ozone dose of about 0.73 mgO₃/mgDOC. However, during one sampling campaign, some short-term unintended reductions of the flow at the ozonation occurred, which resulted in an overall increased average ozone dose of 25 mgO₃/L as ozone production capacity could not be reduced any further. Thus, specific ozone doses achieved during the sampling campaigns varied between 0.63 and 0.97 mgO₃/mgDOC. Most of the 13 ecotoxicological tests were conducted with a final enrichment factor of 10 based on extracts from a solid phase extraction (1000-fold enrichment). As dissolved or suspended compounds have been separated from other compounds in the samples (according to their physical and chemical properties) the ecotoxicity results of enriched samples cannot be compared one-to-one to those which used native samples. Details on the ecotoxicological evaluation can be found in the GoA3.3 report (Stapf et al., 2020).

No negative effects were found for most of the investigated ecotoxicological endpoints such as neurotoxicity, genotoxicity, growth inhibition of the bacteria *Pseudomonas putida* as well as estrogenic and androgenic activity. As no estrogenic effects were observed, an anti-estrogenic potential could be seen in the analyzed samples. In two out of three sampling campaigns, results indicate a reduction of anti-estrogenic potential by the ozonation and a further reduction by the MBBR, whereas no differences could be seen between the sampling points at another sampling campaign. For other tests, e.g. YES/YAS antagonistic properties, no systematic trend was observed, which prevented further evaluation and conclusions from the results obtained. No mutagenic effects were determined with the Ames tests with the strain YG7108 in all samples. In contrast, few unsystematic mutagenic effects were determined in samples from the influent and effluent of the ozonation with the Ames test using strains TA1535 and TA1537. However, in all cases, no mutagenic effects could be observed at the MBBR effluent. In one of the three sampling campaigns a certain growth inhibition of the algae *Desmodesmus subspicatus* was observed in native samples taken from the influent and effluent of the ozonation that were, however, not significantly different. However, no algae growth inhibition was observed in all native samples from the MBBR effluent. Evaluation of *Aliivibrio fischeri* bioluminescence inhibition indicated a slight acute (inhibition above 20 %, below 50 %) or acute toxicity (> 50 % inhibition) at the secondary effluent that was significantly reduced by the combination of ozonation and MBBR post-treatment.

In contrast, conducted *Ceriodaphnia dubia* reproduction tests over 7 days showed an increased mortality of adult *C. dubia* female organisms depending on the applied wastewater concentration. At the highest used sample concentration (98.87%), all adult *C. dubia* died between the first and the sixth day of the test independently of the sampling point. As this circumstance had a strong impact on the evaluation of the reproduction test, results have to be handled with care and cannot directly be compared to those of the other WWTPs as they might not reflect reproduction toxicity effects in the same. Nevertheless, results indicate that the ozonation process does not influence the reproduction of *C. dubia*, whereas MBBR post-treatment had a somewhat negative impact on *C. dubia* reproduction. These findings are somewhat surprising as MBBR post-treatment had beneficial effects towards other ecotoxicological endpoints even though (as described in the MBBR section) the activity in the MBBR full-scale plant is very low and the biomass on the carriers is almost non-existent. During the conduction of the tests, an increasing pH drift within the range of 6 to 9 was observed. The latter might be attributed to the carbonate system and possibly has led to metal toxicity changes and therefore, shifts of the overall toxicity of the samples.

In summary, advanced wastewater treatment with a combination of ozonation and MBBR post-treatment has shown some beneficial impact towards *Aliivibrio fischeri* bioluminescence inhibition. Also, results indicate that the ozonation process is not forming compounds that can cause negative effects on the majority of the evaluated ecotoxicological endpoints. Regarding *Ceriodaphnia dubia* reproduction, it remains unknown if and what exactly caused the consistent increased mortality of adult female organisms.

Additional ecotoxicological tests conducted

An acute toxicity test on *Daphnia magna* was conducted, on samples collected at the three sampling points shown in the figure above, at the Technical University of Denmark. Prior to conducting the test, the stability of the samples in relation to pH and oxygen content was tested. The oxygen concentration was stable during the 30 hours of testing duration. However, the pH increased when the sample came in contact with air, increasing from 7.5 to 8.5 during the 30 hours of the experiment.

After the above mentioned stability test, the samples were filtered to remove any precipitation in the form of salts and calcium carbonate. In general, the filtered samples had a lower and more stable pH. The change in pH corresponds with the equilibrium of the carbonate system, and the precipitate was soluble in acid. This supports the thesis that the high concentrations of calcium carbonate originating from the industrial wastewater can cause pH changes. The acute tests were run for 24 and 48 hours on the filtered sample. Immobile daphnids were not observed in any of the samples, hence it was concluded that wastewater samples from Kalundborg WWTP are not acutely toxic to *Daphnia magna*. However, it should be noted that a direct comparison of acute tests conducted with *D. magna* and reproductions tests with *C. dubia* is not possible.

Environmental risk assessment

The following section describes the risk assessment conducted with the API concentrations in the secondary clarifier effluent and the ozone plant effluent. Within the CWPharma project, the PNEC values for select APIs were identified and used in the subsequent risk assessment. Furthermore, and especially for Kalundborg WWTP, a risk assessment of discharging bromate at concentrations described in section on ozonation by-products was investigated. The risk assessment was conducted by DHIgroup and is provided in the appendix.

Risk from APIs with and without ozonation

The results of the risk assessment conducted before and after ozonation are provided below. Results represent the following:

1. No tertiary treatment (Figure 29). The basis for this figure is the API concentrations in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers.
2. Ozonation as tertiary treatment (Figure 30). The basis for this figure is the API concentrations in the effluent from the ozone plant.

As can be seen in Figure 29, 2 APIs (diclofenac and sulfamethoxazole) are at concentrations posing a high environmental risk if discharged to a receiving water body. An additional 3 APIs (oxazepam, metoprolol, benzotriazole) can raise concern if they are discharged to the receiving water body at concentrations measured at Kalundborg WWTP. The remaining 5 APIs do not raise concern for the receiving water bodies. It should be noted that the concentrations of many APIs are exceptionally low at Kalundborg WWTP due to the dilution with industrial wastewater containing very low concentrations of only a few APIs. This explains why only 10 APIs are discussed in this section.

Figure 29: Risk assessment without any tertiary treatment. PNEC is either based on an according assessment factor (AF) or via a species sensitivity distribution (SSD).

If ozonation is used as a tertiary treatment, the risk for the receiving water bodies is considerably decreased. As can be seen from Figure 30, none of the compounds raise concern for the environment.

Figure 30: Risk assessment *with* tertiary treatment (specific ozone dose of 0.7 mg O₃/ mgDOC). PNEC is either based on an according assessment factor (AF) or via a species sensitivity distribution (SSD).

Together with the results from the ecotoxicity tests presented in section ecotoxicity tests and by-products, it is evident that the ozone treatment decreases the risk from APIs for the environment and receiving water bodies.

Risk from APIs after ozonation versus bromate formation during ozonation

Due to bromide concentrations in the influent to Kalundborg WWTP and the results from the dose-response testing conducted at Kalundborg WWTP, an assessment of the API risk versus the risk of bromate for the environment and receiving water bodies was conducted.

In the risk assessment the Δ RRCR (Risk Characterization Ratio) values are calculated based on the PNEC_{Marine} values for the specific compound as well as the measured concentrations of APIs in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers, the effluent from the ozone plant and the bromate concentration in the effluent from the ozone plant. The report concludes that on the basis of existing knowledge for PNEC_{Marine} values for API species and bromate, the Δ RRCR values increase during ozonation, due to the bromate formation. Hence the risk becomes higher due to bromate when the tertiary treatment is conducted, compared to no tertiary treatment and discharge of APIs at concentrations in the secondary clarifier effluent. Due to the risk from bromate, more tests with marine species were conducted, and the risk assessment was repeated with a new PNEC value for bromate. The second risk assessment showed that the risk to the recipient from bromate was lower than initially calculated, due to high uncertainty factor (100) on the PNEC value for bromate in marine water bodies. Therefore, the overall effect of the ozonation was positive for the marine environment. In the future, more tests with more marine species will be conducted in order to decrease the uncertainty factor from 100 to 50 on the PNEC value for marine species.

The risk assessment only considers the bromate formation and not the formation of bromated halogens and other organic compounds containing brome. This is due to the fact that these specific compounds are not measured during any of the sampling campaigns, however theoretically they will be present, and are also known to have negative effects on health and environment.

Cost analysis for API removal through ozonation

The previously described changes to the ozone system combined with effective tendering on LOX resulted in a large reduction in the price for ozone treatment of the effluent from the secondary clarifiers. An overview of the direct costs related to the ozonation of the wastewater at different times can be seen from Table 9.

Table 9: Overview of the operation cost for ozonation. * Assumed full year operation, no down time of the ozone plant is accounted for.

Period	Flow (m ³ /h)	Specific ozone dose (gO ₃ /gDOC)	Energy (kWh/h)	Energy (€/h)	LOX (€/h)	Total cost (€/h)	Total cost (€/m ³)	Total cost* (€/year)
09/2018	250	1.5	405	34	44.8	78.8	0.36	680,000
01/2019	600	0.56	359	30.1	40.9	71.2	0.12	613,333
07-11/2019	594	0.58	267	17.7	20.9	38.7	0.065	333,333

As can be seen from Table 9, the prices are reduced after installation of new PLCs, enabling a lower ozone production and thus a lower specific dosage of ozone. Further reductions in the prices was observed during 2019 due to a reduction in the prices for electricity from 0,084 €/kWh to 0,055 €/kWh (increased again to 0,067 €/kWh). An even further reduction in the total price was also obtained due to the tendering of LOX, decreasing the price by 50 % for this specific location.

A specific offer from a supplier to install a separate smaller ozone generator into the existing plant has been given. The price is approximately 320.000 €. By installing the smaller generator, approximately 60 % of the energy can be saved and 40 % of the cost for LOX can be saved.

Conclusions

Water quality parameters

- The ozone dose used for removal of API in the wastewater reduces the COD content of the wastewater by approximately 17 %. The reduction is due to the nature of the organic matrix of the COD content in the water from the biotech industries discharging to Kalundborg WWTP.
- The ozone treatment has very little influence on nitrogen species, such as nitrate and ammonia.
- The ozone treatment has no effect on the phosphorous reduction or speciation in the wastewater.
- The ozone treatment results in bromate formation at Kalundborg WWTP, due to incoming bromide from saltwater infiltration in the catchment area. The infiltration amount is approximately 3-3.5 % of the total flow to the wastewater treatment plant.
- The ozone dose is the limiting factor for the bromate formation, since bromide can still be measured in the effluent from the ozone plant.
- Dose-response tests have shown a linear correlation between the bromate formation and the specific ozone dose in the range 0.5 to 1.7 mg O₃/mg DOC.

API reduction

- Many of the APIs detected in the influent to Kalundborg WWTP are below the limit of quantification in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers. This is, depending on the API, either due to aerobic conversion in the activated sludge plant, or due to dilution with industrial wastewater from the biotech industries which contain no or low API concentrations.
- The activated sludge plant at Kalundborg WWTP reduces, on average, 60 % of the APIs coming into the plant.
- The ozone plant at Kalundborg WWTP can reduce the APIs between 28-100 %, depending on the API and the specific ozone setpoint
- At a specific ozone dose at 1.7 mg O₃/mg DOC, a reduction of minimum 98 % for all measured APIs was seen.
- At a specific ozone setpoint of 0.8 mg O₃/mg DOC, an average reduction of 84 % was obtained, corresponding to a bromate concentration of approximately 0.9 mg BrO₃/l.

OPEX and CAPEX

- The OPEX for full-scale operation of the ozone plant has been decreased by 51 % from 680,000 €/year to 333,333 €/year.
- By installing a smaller ozone generator at the plant, the price can be reduced by an additional 48 % from 333,333 €/year to 171,871 €/year.
- Kalundborg utility has conducted a customer survey showing that 80 % of its customers are willing to pay an additional 33.3 €/year/customer in water treatment costs to secure removal of API and xenobiotic compounds.
- If the smaller ozone generator is installed, the rate of return will be between 3-4 years and the prices for the customers will decrease to 13.7 €/(year*customer).
- Based on the data from the CWPharma project, the board of the Kalundborg Utility has decided to operate the full-scale ozonation plant continuously for reduction of APIs and xenobiotic compounds.

Control of ozone dose using online COD sensor

- The online COD sensor was successful in measuring the COD in effluent from the secondary clarifiers.
- The sensor only required cleaning once during the trial period, which is considered a success.
- The sensor could be used for controlling the ozone dose: however, since very little variations occur in the COD concentration from the secondary clarifiers, the sensor has not been installed in the full-scale plant.

Environmental effects

- In general, very little toxicity was detected in the Kalundborg WWTP wastewater, and no difference in the toxicity at the different sample sites of the WWTP was detected.
- The wastewater from Kalundborg WWTP did show an effect on the reproduction test and the algae test. The effect on the reproduction test could be due to the total alkalinity of the water and the high COD content compared to other domestic wastewater treatment plants. Acute tests conducted by the Technical University of Denmark showed that once the total alkalinity in the water was stable, the wastewater had no toxic effect. However, this cannot be definitively concluded and must be further investigated.
- The risk assessment showed that the ozone treatment decreased the risk to the marine environment from APIs.
- The extra risk assessment conducted by DHI initially showed that the risk from the bromate formed during ozonation was higher than the risk from the API species in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers. However, this was due to an uncertainty factor of 1000 on the PNEC marine value for bromate. Further tests with *Acartia tonsa* conducted by DHI decreased the uncertainty factor from 1000 to 100 on the PNEC marine value for bromate. After the risk assessment was reconducted, it showed an overall positive effect of the ozone treatment on the marine environment.

API removal in MBBR pilot plant

- The lab-scale experiments with the carriers from the MBBR plant at Kalundborg WWTP showed that initially, there was generally no biomass on the carriers in the full scale MBBR. The TSS measured in the reference samples is very low. Unfortunately, VSS was not measured on the mass, so it is not possible to distinguish between calcium carbonate precipitation and biomass on the reference carriers. However, knowing the alkalinity of the water, it is safe to assume that a large part of the measured TSS on the reference carriers is precipitate in the form of calcium carbonate.
- The experiments also showed that it is possible to increase the biomass on the carriers (and API removal) significantly by feeding ethanol into the MBBR.
- Many of the API species from the experiment showed removal over time in the MBBR lab-scale tests, however the retention time in the lab-scale tests is several times higher than the 1-2 hours retention time in the full-scale plant, which in the Kalundborg WWTP case, makes full-scale operation of the MBBR plant for API removal difficult.

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Appendix

SI-Table 1: APIs measured at the sampling campaign in January 2019. < LOQ indicates values below limit of quantification.

API	Avg. concentration in the effluent from the secondary clarifiers (mg/l)	Avg. concentration in the effluent from the ozone plant (mg/l)
Venlafaxine	0.21	0.02
Metoprolol	0.76	0.10
Ciprofloxacin	< 1	< 1
Citalopram	0.12	< 0.05
Diclofenac	0.18	< 0.025
Propranolol	< 0.025	< 0.025
Sulfamethoxazole	0.07	< 0.025
Trimethoprim	< 0.023	< 0.023
Iomeprol	< 0.12	< 0.12
Gabapentin	1.21	0.69
Oxazepam	0.11	0.06
Irbesartan	0.02	0.01
Benzotriazole	2.08	0.69
Tramadol	0.90	0.03
Sulfamethizole	0.51	< 0.1
Losartan	0.17	< 0.0125
Carbamazepine	0.11	< 0.05

SI-Table 2: Data from dose response test conducted in February 2019.

Day	Targeted specific ozone dose (mg O ₃ /mg DOC)	DOC concentration (mg DOC/l)	Achieved specific ozone dose (mg O ₃ /mg DOC)
19-02-2020 (Tuesday)	0.4	17	0.5
	0.6	17	0.8
	0.8	17	1.1
	1	15	1.3
	1.2	17	1.6
20-02-2020 (Wednesday)	0.5	17	0.7
	0.7	17	0.9
	0.9	16	1.2
	1.1	17	1.4
	1.3	17	1.7

SI-Table 3: Bromate formation during dose response testing.

Date	Specific ozone dose (mg O ₃ /mg DOC)	Influent bromide concentration (mg Br ⁻ /L)	Effluent bromate concentration (mg BrO ₃ /L)
19-02-2019	0.52	2.74	< 0.005
19-02-2019	0.79	2.6	0.0796
19-02-2019	1.05	2.59	0.205
19-02-2019	1.31	2.62	0.308
19-02-2019	1.57	2.65	0.442
20-02-2019	0.65	2.78	0.0491
20-02-2019	0.92	2.98	0.15
20-02-2019	1.18	2.85	0.295
20-02-2019	1.44	2.84	0.394
20-02-2019	1.7	2.99	0.472

SI-Figure 1: Impact of ozonation on nitrogen species in relation to the specific ozone dose. during response dose experiments in February 2019.

Table 10: Overview on evaluated transformation products, with the according limit of quantification (LOQ) of the analytical method used at Aarhus University.

Parent API	Transformation product	Abbreviation	LOQ (µg/L)
Azithromycin	Azithromycin N-oxides	AZI-NOX	0.2
Carbamazepine	1-(2-benzoic acid)-(1H,3H)-quinazoline-2,4-dione	BaQD	0.05
	CBZ 10,11 epoxides	CBZ-EPX	0.0125
	rac trans 10,11 (dihydro, dihydroxy) CBZ	CBZ-RTN	0.0125
Clarithromycin	Clarithromycin N-oxides	CLM-NOX	0.0125
Diclofenac	Hydroxy diclofenac (mix of 3,4,5)	DCF-OH	0.075
	DCF 2,5 quinone imine	DCF-QIM	0.1
	DCF amide	DCF-AMD	0.05
	DCF benzoic acid	DCF-BZA	0.05
	1-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)indolin-2,3-dione	DCPID	0.5
	2,6-dichlorodiphenylamine	DCPA	0.2
Erythromycin	Erythromycin N-oxides	ERY-NOX	0.05
Tramadol	Tramadol N-oxide	TRA-NOX	0.0125
	N-Desmethyl tramadol	N-DES-TRA	0.0125
Venlafaxine	Venlafaxin N-oxide	VLX-NOX	0.00625

Table 11: Overview on evaluated APIs as well as other substances such as x-ray contrast agents or corrosion inhibitor, which are highlighted in italic. If not stated otherwise, PNEC and assessment factors are based on GoA2.2 report.

Active pharmaceutical ingredient	LOQ (µg/L)	PNEC (µg/L)	Assessment factor	CAS Number	Typical API usage
Atenolol (ATE)	0.025	194	SSD	29122-68-7	antihypertensive
Azithromycin (AZI)	10	N/A	N/A	83905-01-5	antibiotic
<i>Benzotriazole (BTZ)</i>	0.025	19 ^a	50 ^a	95-14-7	<i>corrosion inhibitor, antifreezes</i>
Candesartan (CSC)	0.025	0.42	1000	139481-59-7	antihypertensive
Carbamazepine (CBZ)	0.05	1.28	SSD	298-46-4	antiepileptic
Ciprofloxacin (CFX)	1	0.00511	SSD	85721-33-1	antibiotic
Citalopram (CIT)	0.05	15.4	SSD	59729-33-8	antidepressant
Clarithromycin (CLM)	0.0125	0.00391	SSD	81103-11-9	antibiotic
Clindamycin (CDM)	0.0125	0.014 ^b	1000 ^b	18323-44-9	antibiotic
Diatrizoic acid (DZA)	0.06	N/A	N/A	117-96-4	x-ray contrast agent
Diclofenac (DCF)	0.025	0.0852	SSD	15307-86-5	analgesic and anti-inflammatory
Eprosartan (ESM)	0.05	100	1000	133040-01-4	antihypertensive
Erythromycin (ERY)	0.00625	0.0835	SSD	114-07-8	antibiotic
Gabapentin (GPN)	0.05	100	1000	60142-96-3	antiepileptic
Ibuprofen (IBP)	0.1	0.00012	SSD	15687-27-1	analgesic and anti-inflammatory
<i>Iohexol (IHX)</i>	0.12	N/A	N/A	66108-95-0	<i>x-ray contrast agent</i>
<i>Iomeprol (IMP)</i>	0.12	N/A	N/A	78649-41-9	<i>x-ray contrast agent</i>
<i>Iopamidol (IPD)</i>	0.25	N/A	N/A	60166-93-0	<i>x-ray contrast agent</i>
<i>Iopromide (IPR)</i>	0.25	N/A	N/A	73334-07-3	<i>x-ray contrast agent</i>
Irbesartan (IBS)	0.00625	100	1000	138402-11-6	antihypertensive
Losartan (LSP)	0.0125	7.8	100	114798-26-4	antihypertensive
Metoprolol (MET)	0.05	4.38	SSD	51384-51-1	antihypertensive
Mycophenolic acid (MPA)	0.025	4.2 ^b	50 ^b	24280-93-1	immunosuppressant
Olmesartan (OLS)	0.025	N/A	N/A	144689-63-4	antihypertensive
Oxazepam (OXA)	0.025	0.81	100	604-75-1	treatment of anxiety, insomnia, and alcohol withdrawal syndrome
Phenazone (PNZ)	0.05	N/A	N/A	60-80-0	anti-inflammatory
Propranolol (PRO)	0.025	0.01 ^b	50 ^b	525-66-6	antihypertensive
Roxithromycin (RXM)	0.3	N/A	N/A	80214-83-1	antibiotic
Sotalol (SOT)	0.025	300	1000	3930-20-9	antiarrhythmic agent
Sulfadiazine (SDZ)	0.025	0.135	1000	68-35-9	antibiotic
Sulfamethizole (SMZ)	0.1	N/A	N/A	144-82-1	antibiotic
Sulfamethoxazole (SMX)	0.025	0.0438	SSD	723-46-6	antibiotic
Tramadol (TRA)	0.00625	170	1000	27203-92-5	analgesic and anti-inflammatory
Trimethoprim (TRI)	0.023	508	SSD	738-70-5	antibiotic
Valsartan (VLS)	0.05	125	100	137862-53-4	antihypertensive
Venlafaxine (VLX)	0.0125	3.22	1000	93413-69-5	antidepressant

LOQ = limit of quantification of the analytical method used at Aarhus University, PNEC = predicted no effect concentration, SSD = Species Sensitivity Distribution
a) based on European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), date: 14. April 2020. <https://echa.europa.eu/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/14234/6/1>
b) based on Ågerstrand, M. Derivation of PNECs for 39 pharmaceutical substances. ACES report number 36. Stockholm University. Table 4.

Risikovurdering af API og bromat i spildevand fra Kalundborg Renseanlæg

Inklusive økotoxikologisk test af bromat for kronisk toksiske effekter hos den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*.

Kalundborg Forsyning A/S

Rapport

Juli 2020

Denne rapport er udarbejdet under DHI's ledelsessystem, som er certificeret af Bureau Veritas for overensstemmelse med ISO 9001 for kvalitetsledelse

ISO 9001
Management System Certification

BUREAU VERITAS
Certification Denmark A/S

Godkendt af

01-07-2020

X *Kristina Bkjær*

Approved by

Signed by: Kristina Buus Kjær

Risikovurdering af API og bromat i spildevand fra Kalundborg Renseanlæg

Inklusive økotoxikologisk test af bromat for kronisk toksiske effekter hos den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*.

Udarbejdet for Kalundborg Forsyning A/S
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Projektnummer	11825032
Godkendelsesdato	02.07.2020
Revision	02.07.2020
Klassifikation	Begrænset

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BILAG

BILAG A – Stofdata

BILAG B – RCR for andre miljøfremmede stoffer i udløbet

1 Baggrund og formål

Kalundborg Forsyning har i forbindelse med EU-projektet CW Pharma undersøgt fjernelsen af API'er (aktivstoffer i lægemidler) ved ozonering af spildevand behandlet hos Kalundborg Forsyning i perioden 2018-2020. Efter klaringstankene føres spildevandet gennem et ozonanlæg efterfulgt af MBBR. Gennem to kampagner er der målt på API'er i udløbet fra efterklaringstankene (tilløbet til ozonanlægget) samt i udløbet fra ozonanlægget. Der er desuden gennemført et udvidet prøvetagningsprogram i december 2019, som også inkluderer indløbene til renseanlægget og de interne strømme på renseanlægget. Her er der bl.a. analyseret for 32 API'er på tre punkter i renseanlægget:

1. udløbet fra klaringstankene
2. udløbet fra ozonanlægget
3. udløbet fra MBBR-anlægget

Desuden er der målt for bromid samt for bromat (BrO_3^-), som dannes fra bromid under ozoneringen. Det er fundet, at bromidkoncentrationen i tilløbet til ozonanlægget tilsyneladende er meget stabil og ligger på ca. 1,9 mg Br/l ind og ud fra det aktive slam anlæg, dvs. at der ikke er nogen fjernelse af bromid i aktiv slam anlægget. Der er imidlertid målt bromat i udløbet fra ozonanlægget, og dannelsen af bromat er tilsyneladende proportional med ozondoseringen, hvilket viser, at ozonniveauet i ozonanlægget er den begrænsende faktor for omsætningen af bromid. Der er ikke målt for andre bromforbindelser. Der er næppe tvivl om, at der også vil blive dannet andre organiske bromerede forbindelser ved ozoneringen.

Såvel bromat som API'er udgør en mulig risiko for vandmiljøet, hvorfor der er både fordele og ulemper forbundet med ozonering. Miljøgevinsten er fjernelsen af aktivstoffer (API), mens der er miljøeffekter forbundet med dannelsen af bromate.

Med den baggrund har Kalundborg Forsyning bedt DHI A/S om en sammenlignende miljørisikovurdering af en udledning af 0,2-0,5 mg BrO_3^- /l i forhold til en udledning af API'er uden behandling i ozonanlægget. Derudover ønskes en risikovurdering af slamkvaliteten med henblik på udbringning af slam indeholdende API'er på landbrugsjord.

Denne rapport er en opdateret udgave af den tidligere udarbejdede rapport "Risikovurdering af API og bromat i spildevand fra Kalundborg Renseanlæg" dateret d. 27.04.2020. Efterfølgende er der gennemført økotoksikologisk test af bromat for kronisk toksiske effekter hos den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*. Dette er sket med henblik på at reducere usikkerhedsfaktoren ved bestemmelse af PNEC (Predicted No Effect Concentration) for bromat og dermed øge sikkerheden af rapportens konklusioner vedrørende miljøeffekterne af ozonering.

2 Metode

Miljøriskovurderingen for vandmiljøet er baseret på beregning af forholdet mellem koncentrationen i udløbet, det vil sige efter MBBR (PEC) og nul-effekt-koncentrationen i marint miljø (PNEC(M)):

$$RCR = \frac{PEC}{PNEC(M)}$$

Jo højere RCR er, jo højere er den umiddelbare risiko for påvirkning af vandlevende organismer ved en udledning.

Risikoberegningerne er gennemført for følgende stoffer og forhold:

- 1) Ingen ozon-behandling. Her sættes PEC lig med koncentrationen i udløbet fra de sekundære klaringstanke. Koncentrationen af bromate sættes her til 0 mg/l.
- 2) Ozonering + MBBR. Her sættes PEC lig med koncentrationen i udløbet fra MBBR-anlægget. Bromat-koncentrationen sættes lig med 0,2-0,5 mg BrO₃/l

Beregningen er foretaget for samtlige 26 målte API'er samt for i alt seks nedbrydningsprodukter, som fremkommer fra tramadol, carabemazepine eller diclofenac.

DHI A/S har for samtlige 26 API'er i forbindelse med løsning af andre opgaver afledt PNEC-værdier for stofferne, men har ikke tidligere afledt PNEC-værdier for de analyserede metabolitter. Der er der stort set ingen tilgængelige giftighedsdata for disse metabolitter, hvorfor PNEC for disse er sat lig med PNEC for moderstoffet, hvilket er en konservativ tilgang. Til vurdering af, hvor konservativ denne tilgang er, er der gennemført sammenlignende QSAR-beregninger af den akutte miljøgiftighed for moderstoffet og metabolitterne ved brug af programmet ECOSAR /4/)

Der er foretaget en ABC-vurdering af API'erne og bromate i henhold til Miljøstyrelsens vejledning /1/.

Endelig er de forventelige koncentrationsniveauer af API'er i spildevandsslammet beregnet. Beregningen er foretaget ud fra de målte indløbskoncentrationer til renseanlægget samt fjernelsen med spildevandsslam. Fjernelsen med slam er bestemt ud fra beregning i programmet SimpleTreat /6/.

Det human optag via afgrøder dyrket på landbrugsjord tilført er beregnet ved brug af EUSES, /1/), som giver et konservativt estimat på det humane indtag. Det teoretiske indtag er derefter sammenlignet med det forventelige niveau for acceptabelt dagligt indtag for API'erne, angivet som DNEL_{oral} (DNEL: Derived No Effect Level), TDI (Tolerabelt Dagligt Indtag) eller ADI (Acceptabelt Dagligt Indtag).

3 Resultater

Bilag A viser de anvendte stofdata for både API'erne og bromat. Bilaget indeholder desuden afledningen af PNEC for bromat.

3.1 Vandmiljøet

Koncentrationen af API'erne er målt efter klaringstankene, efter ozonanlægget og efter MBBR anlægget på tre dage i december 2019 (13.12, 14.12 og 15.12). Det antages, at de målte koncentrationer i udløbet fra klaringstankene er lig med udløbskoncentrationen fra Kalundborg renseanlæg hvis der ikke foretages ozonering af spildevandet.

For hver måledato er faldet i risikoen efter ozonering og behandling i MBBR-anlægget for API'erne beregnet:

$$\Delta RCR = \frac{\text{Koncentration efter efterklaring} - \text{Koncentration efter MBBR}}{\text{PNEC(M)}}$$

Tabel 3.1 viser den beregnede ændring i RCR ved ozon og MBBR-behandlingen for de enkelte API'er samt den samlede ændring i RCR:

13.12.2019: $\Delta RCR = 135$

14.12.2019: $\Delta RCR = 148$

15.12.2019: $\Delta RCR = 133$

Gennemsnit: $\Delta RCR = 139$

Bromat dannes imidlertid ved ozoneringen. Koncentrationen af bromat sættes til 0 mg/L, hvis der ikke foretages en ozonering. Bromat er oplyst at blive dannet i en koncentration på mellem 200 – 500 $\mu\text{g BrO}_3^-/\text{l}$.

Et forslag til PNEC(M) for bromat er afledt i denne opgave (se bilag A). Den er fundet ved at indsamle data for målte toksicitet af bromat på vandlevende organismer (typisk laboratorietest, hvor andelen af organismer med målbare negative effekter af stoffet måles ved forskellige koncentrationer) samt en supplerende kronisk test på invertebraten *Acartia Tonsa*. Det drejer sig både om korttidstest (akut toksicitet) og langtidstest (kroniske test). Baseret på de indsamlede data, afledes PNEC ved at identificere den laveste effektkoncentration - typisk EC50 (den koncentration, hvor der er observeret negative effekter på 50% af testorganismene) eller NOEC (den koncentration, hvor der ikke er effekter af stoffet på organismen) eller EC10 (den koncentration, hvor der er observeret negative effekter på 10% af testorganismene) og dividere denne med en usikkerhedsfaktor, som er et udtryk for, hvor mange relevante data, der har været tilgængelig for stoffet. Det vil sige, at jo flere kroniske test på forskellige -især her marine arter - jo lavere usikkerhedsfaktor kan der anvendes. Da der var både akutte og kroniske test for både alger, invertebrater og fisk, blev der anvendt en usikkerhedsfaktor på 100 for marint miljø. Herved er PNEC(M) for bromat bestemt til 11 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (se Bilag A).

På det foreliggende grundlag beregnes bromats bidrag til RCR:

$$\Delta RCR_{\text{bromat}} = 200/11 - 500/11 = 18 - 45 \text{ (per dag).}$$

Ved ozoneringen reduceres risikoforholdet med mellem 135 og 148 målt på tre forskellige dage (gennemsnit 139). Samtidig dannes bromat, som forøger risikofaktoren med 18 – 45. Det betyder, at selvom bromatdannelsen umiddelbart bidrager til en øgning i risikoforholdet, vil

ozoneringen samlet set giver anledning til en samlet reduceret risikofaktor på mellem 90 og 130 per dag.

Til vurdering af, om dette er højt eller lavt, er bidraget til RCR for en række miljøfremmede stoffer og tungmetaller i udløbet fra Kalundborg Renseanlæg beregnet. Beregningerne baserer sig på målte koncentrationer i udløbet fra Kalundborg Renseanlæg over to kampagner i slutningen af august – begyndelsen af september, 2016 /10/. Gennemsnittet af de målte udløbskoncentrationer i de to døgn er divideret med deres respektive PNEC-værdier. Resultaterne fremgår af bilag B. Det samlede bidrag til RCR fra disse miljøfremmede stoffer beregnes til 108, dvs. bidraget fra de øvrige stoffer er i samme størrelsesorden, som den beregnede samlede reducerede risikofaktor som ozoneringen giver anledning til. De største bidragsydere til de 108 er de fire stoffer: Perfluorooctan syre (PFOA), perfluorooctan sulfonat (PFOS), kobber og kobolt. Disse fire stoffer bidrager jævnt før Bilag B alene til RCR med 102.

Det vil sige, at ozoneringen med dannelse af bromat, men med samtidig reduktion i udledningen af API'er giver anledning til en betydelig positiv ændring i risikoen sammenlignet med udledning af miljøfremmede stoffer fra Kalundborg Renseanlæg.

Følgende forhold skal dog tages i betragtning:

- Bromat vil blive nedbrudt til bromid i miljøet primært under anaerobe forhold og dermed reduceres toksiciteten. Halveringstiden af bromat i havvand er dog tidligere vurderet til at være over 1/2 år /8/, hvorfor bromat generelt betegnes som persistent i vandmiljøet. De API'er, som umiddelbart bidrager mest til RCR-erne, er dog også langsomt nedbrydelige med beregnede nedbrydningstider i størrelsesordenen måneder (fx Tramadol, Venlafaxine) og uger-måneder diclofenac og sulfamethizole).
- Det skal også nævnes, at andre bromerede og chlorerede organiske forbindelser vil blive dannet ved ozoneringen. Dette drejer sig fx om bromoform, chloroform, andre halogerede trihalomethaner, bromo- og chloro-eddikesyrer, hvoraf nogle af disse er kendte som værende sundheds- og/eller miljøskadelige. Disse stoffer vil også bidrage med en forøgelse af den samlede RCR efter ozoneringen og dermed i udløbet fra MBBR-anlægget.

Tabel 3.1 Beregnede ændringer i risikoen for API'erne ved MBBR-behandlingen. i.d.: under detektionsgrænsen.

API µg/L	Efter sekundær klaringstank			Efter MBBR			ΔRCR	ΔRCR	ΔRCR
	13.12.2019	14.12.2019	15.12.2019	13.12.2019	14.12.2019	15.12.2019	13.12.2019	14.12.2019	15.12.2019
Atenolol	< 0,013	< 0,013	< 0,013	< 0,013	< 0,013	< 0,013	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
Sotalol	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
Iohexol	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
Iopamidol	0,707	0,594	0,139	0,345	0,363	0,129	0,009	0,006	<0,001
Iomerprol	0,680	0,557	0,147	0,401	0,412	0,132	0,003	0,001	<0,001
Gabapentin	1,615	1,625	1,700	0,504	0,640	0,658	0,011	0,010	0,010
Sulfadiazine	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
Trimethoprim	0,029	0,025	0,023	0,010	0,012	0,011	0,003	0,002	0,002
Sulfamethoxazole	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
Metoprolol	0,517	0,536	0,523	0,176	0,246	0,236	0,055	0,047	0,046
Tramadol	0,584	0,627	0,632	0,211	0,271	0,282	37,300	35,600	34,900
Sulfamethizole	0,652	0,792	0,811	0,188	0,273	0,372	39,343	44,025	37,246
Venlafaxine	0,185	0,199	0,188	0,078	0,089	0,077	10,690	11,057	11,138
Trimethoprim	0,029	0,025	0,023	0,010	0,012	0,011	0,003	0,002	0,002
Benzotriazole	1,970	2,255	2,545	0,655	0,880	1,018	14,617	15,275	16,972
Propranolol	< 0,050	< 0,050	< 0,050	< 0,050	< 0,050	< 0,050	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
Citalopram	0,108	0,105	0,095	0,039	0,047	0,045	0,086	0,073	0,062

API µg/L	Efter sekundær klaringstank			Efter MBBR			ΔRCR	ΔRCR	ΔRCR
	13.12.2019	14.12.2019	15.12.2019	13.12.2019	14.12.2019	15.12.2019	13.12.2019	14.12.2019	15.12.2019
Roxithromycin	0,054	0,061	0,052	0,017	0,024	0,026	0,109	0,108	0,076
Erythromycin	0,042	0,041	0,045	0,018	0,015	0,025	1,221	1,305	0,986
Clarithromycin	0,043	0,038	0,030	0,016	0,019	0,018	2,279	1,625	0,981
Carbamazepine	0,086	0,083	0,074	0,026	0,034	0,033	1,195	0,981	0,825
Diclofenac	0,163	0,179	0,180	0,073	0,070	0,102	18,020	21,795	15,500
Mycophenolic acid	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
Irbesartan	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
Losartan	0,242	0,243	0,286	0,068	0,097	0,111	0,007	0,006	0,007
Oxazepam	0,074	0,103	0,084	< 0,050	< 0,050	0,047	0,471	1,066	0,741
Nedbrydningsprodukter									
N-DES-TRA	0,241	0,264	0,221	0,082	0,103	0,102	15,900	16,050	11,855
CBZ-RTN	0,138	0,162	0,140	0,064	0,087	0,095	1,481	1,491	0,898
TRA-NOX	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
DCF-OH	< 0,025	< 0,025	0,029	0,065	0,036	< 0,025	-8,062 ¹⁾	-2,221 ¹⁾	0,842
BaQD	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	< 0,100	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.
CBZ-EPX	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	< 0,025	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.

API µg/L	Efter sekundær klaringstank			Efter MBBR			ΔRCR	ΔRCR	ΔRCR
	13.12.2019	14.12.2019	15.12.2019	13.12.2019	14.12.2019	15.12.2019	13.12.2019	14.12.2019	15.12.2019
Sum ΔRCR							134,74	148,31	133,09

¹⁾Stoffet bliver sandsynligvis dannes under ozoneringen.

3.2 Slam

Som nævnt er fjernelsen af API'erne beregnet ved brug af programmet SimpleTreat /6/. Koncentrationen i spildevandsslam er herefter beregnet af formlen:

$$PEC(\text{slam}) = \frac{Q \cdot \text{Indløbskoncentrationen} \cdot f_{\text{slam}}}{\text{Slammængde}}$$

Hvor

Q er spildevandsmængden, som er sat til 6,010 mill. m³ per år

Slammængde er sat til 1000 tons tørstof per år

f_{slam} fjernelsesgrad for de enkelte aktivstoffer

Det humane daglige indtag af stoffer fra afgrøder dyrket på marker gødet med spildevandsslam er beregnet ved hjælp af EUSES /1/ og dets standardparametre.

Resultaterne af beregningerne fremgår af Tabel 3.2. Den beregnede koncentration af API'erne i slam varierer fra < 0,01 µg/kg ts til ca. 600 µg/kg ts – afhængigt af aktivstof, indløbskoncentration samt binding til slam.

Endvidere fremgår det af Tabel 3.2, at det beregnede humane indtag er under 0,001 mg/kg Ig/d for samtlige API'er. For enkelte af API'erne er der tidligere afledt en ADI:

- Carbamazepine: værdier for ADI mellem 2,8 – 95 µg/kg Ig/d er tidligere foreslået (refereret i Ricardo, 2014). Forfatterne foreslår selv en værdi på 22 µg/kg Ig/d
- Carbamazepine epoxide: En værdi på 59 µg/kg Ig/d /5/
- Benzotriazol (ikke et API): DNEL_{oral} = 540 µg/kg Ig/d er foreslået i REACH registreringsdossieret for stoffet /7/

Der er afledt DNEL_{oral} for enkelte API'er, som der ikke er analyseret i måleprogrammet på Kalundborg renseanlæg. De afledte værdier af DNEL_{oral} af er alle væsentligt over 0,001 mg/kg Ig/d. og dermed forventes ingen risiko ved indtag af afgrøder dyrket på landbrugsjord, hvor der har været udspremt spildevandsslam. Alle værdier er hentet fra deres REACH registreringsdossier /7/.

- Quinin: 300 µg/kg Ig/d
- Paracetamol: 1.702 µg/kg Ig/d
- Choline chloride: 12.000 µg/kg Ig/d
- Diethyl carbonate: 1.000 µg/kg Ig/d
- Etidronic acid: 1.700 µg/kg Ig/d
- Guanidine hydrochloride: 500 µg/kg Ig/d
- N,N'-dimethylaniline: 629 µg/kg Ig/d
- Niacinamide 100% DC: 12.500 µg/kg Ig/d
- Nicotine: 76,5 µg/kg Ig/d
- Orthoformic acid trimethylester: 1.730 µg/kg Ig/d
- Salicylic acid: 1.000 µg/kg Ig/d
- Lithium: 9.500 µg/kg Ig/d
- Piperacillin: 2.660 µg/kg Ig/d

Da de beregnede humane optag via afgrøder dyrket på slamgødet landbrugsjord, er væsentligt lavere end kendte nuleffekt-niveauer for API'er vurderes det, at API'erne næppe vil udgøre en risiko for mennesker, hvis spildevandsslammet spredes ud på landbrugsjorden.

Tabel 3.2 Beregnede fjernelses (reduktionsfaktor) med slam, koncentration i spildevandsslam samt humant indtag via planter dyrket på landbrugsjord, hvor spildevandsslam er anvendt.

API	Brøkdeltil slam f_{slam}	Beregnet koncentration i spildevandsslam			Beregnet human dagligt indtag		
		$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg TS}$			$\text{mg}/\text{kg Ig}/\text{d}$		
		13.12. 2019	14.12. 2019	15.12. 2019	13.12. 2019	14.12. 2019	15.12. 2019
Atenolol	3,55E-04	0,07	0,07	0,08	4,1E-08	3,9E-08	4,4E-08
Sotalol	2,18E-04	0,03	0,03	0,03	1,5E-08	1,5E-08	1,5E-08
Iohexol	5,06E-07	<0,01	<0,01	<0,01	5,0E-10	9,6E-11	7,9E-11
Iopamidol	1,64E-06	0,12	0,05	<0,01	2,4E-08	1,1E-08	1,7E-09
Iomerprol	8,21E-07	0,06	0,03	<0,01	9,9E-09	4,5E-09	6,8E-10
Gabapentin	1,53E-05	0,72	0,73	0,62	5,3E-08	5,4E-08	4,6E-08
Sulfadiazine	1,26E-04	0,02	0,02	0,02	7,5E-09	6,3E-09	6,3E-09
Trimethoprim	4,57E-04	0,30	0,25	0,19	1,8E-07	1,5E-07	1,1E-07
Sulfamethoxazole	5,15E-04	0,51	0,43	0,36	3,3E-07	2,8E-07	2,3E-07
Metoprolol	2,61E-05	0,14	0,13	0,11	2,3E-08	2,2E-08	1,9E-08
Tramadol	1,29E-02	55	49	42	1,1E-05	1,0E-05	8,6E-06
Sulfamethizole	7,47E-04	4,8	6,0	4,6	3,4E-06	4,2E-06	3,2E-06
Venlafaxine	3,33E-04	0,43	0,44	0,39	2,3E-07	2,3E-07	2,1E-07
Trimethoprim	4,57E-04	0,30	0,25	0,19	1,8E-07	1,5E-07	1,1E-07
Benzotriazole	2,04E-03	31	32	32	1,9E-05	2,0E-05	2,0E-05
Propranolol	5,55E-04	0,17	0,17	0,17	1,1E-07	1,1E-07	1,1E-07
Citalopram	9,17E-02	90	88	75	1,9E-05	1,8E-05	1,5E-05
Roxithromycin	3,55E-03	1,9	1,0	1,8	1,8E-06	9,5E-07	1,8E-06
Erythromycin	4,28E-02	18	25	16	5,9E-06	8,0E-06	5,2E-06
Clarithromycin	5,11E-02	18	15	14	5,0E-06	4,1E-06	3,9E-06
Carbamazepine	3,70E-03	1,9	1,9	1,5	7,2E-07	7,1E-07	5,7E-07
Diclofenac	1,63E-01	184	175	153	5,3E-06	5,0E-06	4,4E-06
Mycophenolic acid	1,55E-02	43	40	32	7,4E-06	6,9E-06	5,6E-06
Irbesartan	8,25E-01	599	124	172	2,1E-04	4,3E-05	5,9E-05
Losartan	3,66E-02	492	577	401	3,2E-05	3,8E-05	2,6E-05
Oxazepam	2,51E-02	12	13	12	1,2E-06	1,2E-06	1,2E-06
N-DES-TRA	2,69E-02	45	38	31	2,0E-05	1,7E-05	1,4E-05
CBZ-RTN							
TRA-NOX	5,46E-05	<0,01	<0,01	<0,01	1,6E-09	1,6E-09	1,6E-09
DCF-OH	1,27E-01	34	22	19	6,4E-06	4,1E-06	3,7E-06
BaQD	1,42E-02	8,5	8,5	8,5	5,8E-06	5,8E-06	5,8E-06
CBZ-EPX	8,78E-04	0,13	0,13	0,13	1,2E-07	1,2E-07	1,2E-07

4 Konklusioner

Som følge af bromatdannelse ved ozonering af spildevandet på Kalundborg Renseanlæg vil dette umiddelbart resultere i en forøgelse i RCR for udledningen til vandområdet.

Det skal fremhæves, at bromat under anaerobe forhold vil blive nedbrudt til bromid i miljøet – dog med halveringstider over ½ år i havvand. De API'er, som umiddelbart bidrager mest til RCR-erne, er også langsomt nedbrydelige med beregnede nedbrydningstider i størrelsesordenen måneder (fx Tramadol, Venlafaxine) og uger-måneder diclofenac og sulfamethizole).

Samlet set vil ozoneringen med dannelse af bromat, men med samtidig reduktion i udledningen af API'er give anledning til en betydelig positiv ændring i den samlede risiko for vandmiljøet også ved sammenlignet med udledning af andre miljøfremmede stoffer fra Kalundborg Renseanlæg.

Den beregnede koncentration af API'erne i slam varierer fra under 0,01 til 600 µg/kg ts – afhængighed hvilket aktivstof der er tale om samt indløbskoncentrationen og stoffets binding til slam. Udgangspunktet for beregningerne af koncentrationerne i slammet har været at ozoneringen ikke påvirker tilstedeværelsen af API'er i slammet. Det vurderes, at API'erne næppe vil udgøre en risiko for mennesker, hvis spildevandsslammet spredes ud på landbrugsjord.

5 Referencer

- /1/ EUSES. Program til miljørisikovurdering. Det anvendte program er excel-version, som er udviklet for CEFIC.
- /2/ Miljøstyrelsen: *Tilslutning af industrispildevand til offentlige spildevandsanlæg*, Vejledning fra Miljøstyrelsen nr. 2, 2006
- /3/ Ricardo-AEA/R/ED59005 (2014): Toxicological evaluation for pharmaceuticals in drinking water. Objective 6: Final report. Report for Drinking Water Inspectorate, Issue Number 2 Date 26/06/2014
- /4/ US EPA (2000): ECOSAR. ECOSAR Class Program v1.11. Program til beregning af stoffers miljøgiftighed. Kan frit hentes fra nettet.
- /5/ US EPA (2000): Epi Suite. Program til beregning af fysisk-kemiske data for kemiske stoffer. Kan frit hentes fra nettet.
- /6/ SimpleTreat. En delvis selvstændighed del af EUSES. Program til beregning af miljøfremmede stoffers skæbne i renselanlæg. Del af EUSES.
- /7/ On-line database for registrerede kemiske stoffer. Registreringsdata kan hentes fra <http://echa.eu>.
- /8/ Environment Canada Health Canada (2010): Screening Assessment for the Challenge Bromic acid, potassium salt (Potassium bromate). Chemical Abstracts Service Registry Number 7758-01-2.

BILAG

BILAG A – Stofdata

A Stofdata

Tabel 5.1 Stofdata for de undersøgte API'er og bromat

API		CAS-RN	Mw	logKow	H	Aerob bionedbrydelighed	PNEC _F	PNEC _M	Kommentarer
			g/mol		Pa·mol/m ³		µg/L	µg/L	
Bromat	A		128	-	-	Uorganisk,	11	1,1	Bromat har en harmoniseret klassificering med Carc. 1B H350 (udløser A-scoren); Acute Tox 3 H301; Ox. Sol 1 H271. Det vil forventeligt reduceres til bromid-ionen i miljøet. Se bilag A for afledningen af PNEC
API'er									
Atenolol	A	29122-68-7	266,34	0,5	4,0E-08	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	100	10	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Sotalol	B	959-24-0	293,81	0,24	2,4E-13	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	62	6,2	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Iohexol	C	66108-95-0	821	-3,05	7,7E-02	ikke bionedbrydeligt	1000	100	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger

API		CAS-RN	Mw g/mol	logKow	H Pa·mol/m ³	Aerob bionedbrydelighed	PNEC _F µg/L	PNEC _M µg/L	Kommentarer
Iopamidol	C	60166-93-0	777	-2,42	1,2E-20	ikke bionedbrydeligt	410	41	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Iomerprol	C	78649-41-9	777,09	-2,79	3,1E-30	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder ikke kriterierne	1000	100	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Gabapentin	A	60142-96-3	171,24	-1,1	3,2E-11	let bionedbrydeligt	100	100	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Sulfadiazine	B	68-35-9	250,28	-0,09	1,6E-05	ikke bionedbrydeligt	4,6	4,6	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Trimethoprim	A	738-70-5	290,32	0,6	1,2E-07	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder ikke kriterierne	62	6,2	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Sulfamethoxazole	A	723-46-6	253,28	0,7	1,1E-06	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	0,59	0,059	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Metoprolol	B	56392-17-7	267,37	-0,9	2,1E-06	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	62	6,2	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Tramadol	B	27203-92-5	263,38	2,4	1,4E-05	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder ikke kriterierne	0,1	0,01	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Sulfamethizole	B	144-82-1	270,33	0,9	9,3E-09	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	0,118	0,0118	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger

API		CAS-RN	Mw g/mol	logKow	H Pa·mol/m ³	Aerob bionedbrydelighed	PNEC _F µg/L	PNEC _M µg/L	Kommentarer
Venlafaxine	B	99300-78-4	313,87	0,43	1,9E-12	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder ikke kriterierne	0,1	0,01	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Trimethoprim	A	738-70-5	290,32	0,6	1,2E-07	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder ikke kriterierne	62	6,2	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Benzotriazole	B	95-14-7	119,3	1,44	1,8E-05	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	0,9	0,09	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Propranolol	A	318-98-9	295,81	0,74	4,1E-12	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	0,02	0,002	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Citalopram	B	59729-33-8	324,4	3,5	1,6E-04	ikke bionedbrydeligt	8	0,8	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Roxithromycin	A	80214-83-1	837,07	1,7	6,2E-23	ikke bionedbrydeligt	3,4	0,34	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Erythromycin	A	114-07-8	733,95	3,06	4,0E-20	ikke bionedbrydeligt	0,2	0,02	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Clarithromycin	A	81103-11-9	747,97	3,16	6,8E-20	ikke bionedbrydeligt	0,12	0,012	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Carbamazepine	A	298-46-4	236,28	1,76	1,6E-04	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	0,5	0,05	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger

API		CAS-RN	Mw g/mol	logKow	H Pa·mol/m ³	Aerob bionedbrydelighed	PNEC _F µg/L	PNEC _M µg/L	Kommentarer
Diclofenac	A	15307-86-5	296,15	3,9	5,4E-04	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	0,05	0,005	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Mycophenolic acid	A	24280-93-1	433,51	2,5	1,6E-11	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder ikke kriterierne	0,1	0,01	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Irbesartan	B	138402-11-6	428,54	6	1,2E-09	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	704	70,4	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Losartan	B	124750-99-8	461,01	3,01	3,0E-22	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	245	24,5	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Oxazepam	A	604-75-1	286,72	2,8	8,9E-10	potentielt bionedbrydeligt, opfylder kriterierne	0,5	0,05	ABC-vurdering og afledning af PNEC fra tidligere vurderinger
Nedbrydningsprodukter fra API'er									
N-DES-TRA	B		249,36	2,8	1,60E-05	ikke bionedbrydeligt	0,1	0,01	ABC og PNEC sat lig med PNEC for moderstoffet Tramadol
CBZ-RTN	A					ikke bionedbrydeligt	0,5	0,05	ABC og PNEC sat lig med PNEC for moderstoffet Carbamazepine
TRA-NOX	B	147441-56-3	266,36	-0,54	1,2E-16	ikke bionedbrydeligt	0,1	0,01	ABC og PNEC sat lig med PNEC for moderstoffet Tramadol

API		CAS-RN	Mw g/mol	logKow	H Pa·mol/m ³	Aerob bionedbrydelighed	PNEC _F µg/L	PNEC _M µg/L	Kommentarer
DCF-OH	A		312,15	3,7	5,0E-11	ikke bionedbrydeligt	0,05	0,005	ABC og PNEC sat lig med PNEC for moderstoffet Diclofenac
BaQD	A		282,26	2,45	5,6E-10	ikke bionedbrydeligt	0,5	0,05	ABC og PNEC sat lige med Stoffet dannet ved ozonering af Carabemazepin
CBZ-EPX	A		252,27	0,95	9,3E-06	ikke bionedbrydeligt	1	0,1	ABC og PNEC sat lig med PNEC for moderstoffet Carabemazepine

A.1 Afledning af PNEC for bromat

I et ældre review fra 1997 blev der udarbejdet en oversigt over effekter af bromat på vandlevende organismer /4/.

Tabel 5.2 Oversigt over data for effekter af bromat på vandlevende organismer fra /4/.

Alger							
Test species	Common name	Life stage	Test chemical (N/M)	Endpoint	Time	Conc. BrO ₃ ⁻ (mg liter ⁻¹)	Confidence interval
Freshwater species—no data available							
Estuarine and marine species							
<i>Glenodinium halli</i>	Dinoflagellate	LC	NaBrO ₃ (N)	EC ₂₅ (growth)	ns	>13.6 ^a	ns
<i>G. halli</i>	Dinoflagellate	LC	NaBrO ₃ (N)	EC ₅₀ (growth)	ns	>13.6 ^a	ns
<i>Isochrysis galbana</i>	Microflagellate	LC	NaBrO ₃ (N)	EC ₂₅ (growth)	ns	>13.6 ^b	ns
<i>I. galbana</i>	Microflagellate	LC	NaBrO ₃ (N)	EC ₅₀ (growth)	ns	>13.6 ^a	ns
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Filamentous diatom	LC	NaBrO ₃ (N)	EC ₂₅ (growth)	ns	>13.6 ^c	ns
<i>S. costatum</i>	Filamentous diatom	LC	NaBrO ₃ (N)	EC ₅₀ (growth)	ns	>13.6 ^a	ns
<i>Thalassiosira pseudonana</i>	Unicellular diatom	LC	NaBrO ₃ (N)	EC ₂₅ (growth)	ns	>13.6 ^a	ns
Invertebrater							
Test species	Common name	Life stage	Test chemical (N/M)	Endpoint	Time	Conc. BrO ₃ ⁻ (mg liter ⁻¹)	Confidence interval
Freshwater species							
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Water flea	JU	NaBrO ₃ (N)	LC ₅₀	48 h	179	ns
<i>Polycelis nigra</i>	Planarian	ns	NaBrO ₃ (N)	LC ₅₀	48 h	2558	ns
Estuarine and marine species							
<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	Pacific oyster	LA	BrO ₃ (ns)	EC ₅₀	48 h	30	ns
<i>Crassostrea virginica</i>	Eastern oyster	LA	BrO ₃ (ns)	EC ₅₀	48 h	0.05–0.1 ^a	Not applicable
<i>Macoma inguinata</i>	Bentnose clam	ns	BrO ₃ (ns)	LC ₅₀	72 h	<880 ^b	ns
<i>Neomysis awatschensis</i>	Mysid shrimp	AD	BrO ₃ (ns)	LC ₅₀	24 h	176	ns
<i>Pandalus danae</i>	Coonstripe shrimp	ns	BrO ₃ (ns)	LC ₅₀	72 h	<880 ^b	ns
<i>Protothaca staminea</i>	Littleneck shrimp	ns	BrO ₃ (ns)	LC ₅₀	72 h	<880 ^b	ns

Fisk							
Test species	Common name	Life stage	Test chemical (N/M)	Endpoint	Time	Conc. BrO ₃ ⁻ (mg liter ⁻¹)	Confidence interval
Freshwater fish—no data available							
Saltwater fish							
<i>Cymatogaster aggregata</i>	Shiner perch	ns	BrO ₃ (ns)	LC ₅₀	72 h	<880 ^a	ns
<i>Leiostomus xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	1 day	698	493–1946
<i>L. xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	2 days	518	368–ns
<i>L. xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	3 days	468	268–765
<i>L. xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	4 days	427	322–685
<i>L. xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	5 days	415	323–605
<i>L. xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	6 days	399	304–590
<i>L. xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	7 days	379	294–528
<i>L. xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	8 days	337	295–387
<i>L. xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	9 days	296	258–337
<i>L. xanthurus</i>	Spot	JU	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	10 days	279	244–317
<i>Morone saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	EM (hatch)	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	24 h	697	313–975
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	LA	NaBrO ₃ (M)	EC ₅₀	36 h	103	75–139
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	LA	NaBrO ₃ (M)	EC ₅₀	48 h	43	30–57
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	LA	NaBrO ₃ (M)	EC ₅₀	72 h	40	28–51
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	LA	NaBrO ₃ (M)	EC ₅₀	96 h	31	21–40
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	PL	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	2 days	605	507–1007
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	PL	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	3 days	492	439–621
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	PL	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	4 days	404	350–480
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	PL	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	5 days	313	273–366
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	PL	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	6 days	230	200–271
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	PL	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	7 days	197	172–229
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	PL	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	8 days	177	148–210
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	PL	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	9 days	148	114–185
<i>M. saxatilis</i>	Striped bass	PL	NaBrO ₃ (M)	LC ₅₀	10 days	93	ns
<i>Oncorhynchus keta</i>	Chum salmon	JU	BrO ₃ (ns)	LC ₅₀	96 h	512	ns

EM: embryo; LA, larve; PL, pro-larve; JU, juvenil; N, nominal; M, målt; ns, ikke specificeret (not specified).

Supplerende data er givet i nedenstående Tabel 5.3.

Tabel 5.3 Supplerende data for effekter af bromat på vandlevende organismer

Effektkoncentration	Primær reference	Refereret i	Klimi sch score	Teststof
EC10 (Larval development ratio, <i>Acartia Tonsa</i> , 5 dage) = 1,8 mg bromat/L NOEC (Larval development ratio, <i>Acartia Tonsa</i> , 5 dage) = 1,3 mg bromat/L	/11/	-	1	Na-BrO ₃
NOEC (10d, <i>Morone saxatillis</i>): 280 mg/L=215 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /L	/6/	IMO database for Ballast Water Chemicals, GISIS		
LC50(4d, <i>Dario rerio</i>) 931 mg/L=714 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /L	/9/	HSDB: Hazardous Substances Data Bank https://www.echemportal.org/echemportal/content/participants/8		K-BrO ₃
LC50(4d, <i>Dario rerio</i>) 1066 mg/L=817 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /L	/9/	HSDB: Hazardous Substances Data Bank https://www.echemportal.org/echemportal/content/participants/8		K-BrO ₃
LC50(76 timer efter befrugtning, <i>Dario rerio</i>) 65,4 mM = 8371 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /l EC50(76 timer efter befrugtning, <i>Dario rerio</i>): 49,2 mM = 6298 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /l EC20 (76 timer efter befrugtning, <i>Dario rerio</i>) 40,7 mM = 5110 mg BrO₃⁻/l	/7/		2	
EC50(48 timer, <i>Daphnia magna</i>): >100 mg/l (EU C.2: Acute Toxicity for <i>Daphnia</i>)		REACH registration dossier "sodium bromate"	1	Na-BrO ₃
EC50(48 timer, <i>Daphnia magna</i>): 55,3 mg/l =46,9 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /L EC50(96 timer, <i>Daphnia magna</i>): 46,8 mg/l = 39,7 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /L (US EPA, 2002. EPA-821-R-02-012, 5. ed. U.S)	/3/	HSDB: Hazardous Substances Data Bank https://www.echemportal.org/echemportal/content/participants/8	2	Na-BrO ₃
LC50(7 dage, <i>Hyalella azteca</i>) 1,1 mg BrO₃⁻/L		Appendix 2 af /1/	2	Na-BrO ₃
E ₉ C50 (72 timer, <i>Desmodesmus subspicatus</i>): >100 mg/L	-	REACH registreringsdossi	1	K-BrO ₃

Effektkoncentration	Primær reference	Refereret i	Klimi sch score	Teststof
NOE_gC (72 timer, <i>Desmodesmus subspicatus</i>): 31,6 mg/L = 24,2 mg BrO₃⁻/L (OECD Guideline 201, Freshwater Alga and Cyanobacteria, Growth Inhibition Test)		er "potassium bromate"		
EC50 (72 timer, <i>Scenedesmus obliquus</i>): >100 mg/L (standard toxic testing method)	/9/	HSDB: Hazardous Substances Data Bank https://www.echemportal.org/echemportal/content/participants/8		Na-BrO ₃
EC50 (96 timer, <i>Scenedesmus obliquus</i>): 738 mg/L = 626 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /L (standard toxic testing method)	/9/	HSDB: Hazardous Substances Data Bank https://www.echemportal.org/echemportal/content/participants/8		Na-BrO ₃
EC50 (96 timer, <i>Isochrysis galbana</i>): 540 mg/L = 458 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /l NOE _g C(72 timer, <i>Isochrysis galbana</i>): 5280 mg/L = 4478 mg BrO ₃ ⁻ /l (USEPA, 2002. EPA-821-R-02-013, 4 ed. – afvigelse: justeret for marine organismer)	/3/		2	Na-BrO ₃

Der er primært fundet effektdata for alger, hvirvelløse dyr og fisk. Den akutte toksicitet af bromat er generelt større end eller lig med ca. 30 mg BrO₃⁻/L. Tidlige livsstadier af fisk (for eksempel nyudklækkede larver) er tilsyneladende mere følsomme over for bromat end de efterfølgende pro-larve eller juvenile livsfasen. Fiskembryoer før udklækning er imidlertid relativt ufølsomme over for bromat, formentlig på grund af den beskyttende funktion af ægmembranen. Baseret på størstedelen af de tilgængelige data for alger, invertebrater og fisk, kan bromat derfor betragtes som værende giftigt, med E(L)C50-værdier fra 31 til >100 mg BrO₃⁻/L. Den akutte giftighed er tilsyneladende på samme niveau for alger, krebsdyr og fisk.

Undersøgelser offentliggjort af /7/ for østlige østers (*Crassostrea virginica*) antyder signifikante reduktioner i embryoudvikling ved koncentrationer så lave som 0,05 mg BrO₃⁻/L, skønt der blev observeret en uforklarlig stigning i embryoudviklingen ved 10 mg BrO₃⁻/L. I modsætning blev der målt en 48-timers EC50 af 30 mg BrO₃⁻/L baseret på en lignende test ved brug af den tæt beslægtede stillehavsøsters, *Crecelius* (1979). Forklaringen af denne betydelige variation i følsomheden af embryo-larver over for bromat er ikke umiddelbart åbenlys, da en lignende følsomhed af de to arter må forventes. I en gentaget test af embryoudviklingen i stillehavsøsteren målt en 24-timers EC50-værdi på 170 mg BrO₃⁻/L og en 24-timers NOEC på 32 mg BrO₃⁻/L, som er sammenlignelig med den 24-timers LOEC på 56 mg BrO₃⁻/L, der blev

målt i den tidligere undersøgelse /4/. Det vurderes derfor, at testen med *Crassostrea virginica* ikke bør inddrages ved afledningen af PNEC-værdierne.

Videre er der målt en forholdsvis lav LC50 værdi for ferskvandsamfipoden *Hyalella azteca* på 1,1 mg BrO₃⁻/L (7-dage). Denne 7-dages test er dog ikke udført efter en standardmetode. Selvom arten især bruges i laboratoriet til sedimenttoksicitets- og bioakkumuleringstest, er den dog sandsynligvis også anvendelig til testning af toksicitet i overfladevand.

Der er tilgængelige kroniske værdier for alger, fisk og invertebrater. Invertebrater viste sig den mest følsomme i test for akut giftighed. Derfor anvendes en usikkerhedsfaktor på 10 for ferskvand og en usikkerhedsfaktor på 100 for marint vand /1/, hvorved følgende PNEC-værdier bestemmes:

$$\text{PNEC(F)} = 1,1 \text{ mg BrO}_3^-/\text{L}/10 = 110 \text{ }\mu\text{g BrO}_3^-/\text{L}$$

$$\text{PNEC(M)} = 1,1 \text{ mg BrO}_3^-/\text{L}/100 = 11 \text{ }\mu\text{g BrO}_3^-/\text{L}$$

Referencer

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BILAG B – RCR for andre miljøfremmede stoffer i udløbet

B PEC/PNEC for øvrige miljøfremmede stoffer i udløbet fra Kalundborg Renseanlæg

Stof	Enheden	Målte koncentrationer i udløbet fra Kalundborg Renseanlæg i 2016 /10/)			KVKK $\mu\text{g/l}$	EU eller DK krav	RCR
		22.-28.08. 2016	29.08-04.09. 2016	Gnm. for de to kampagner			
Barium (Ba) filtreret	$\mu\text{g/l}$	1,7	2	1,85	5,8	DK	0,3
Bly (Pb)	$\mu\text{g/l}$	0,9	0,8	0,85	1,3	EU	0,7
Krom (Cr)	$\mu\text{g/l}$	1,1	1,4	1,25	3,4	DK	0,4
Kobolt (Co) filtreret	$\mu\text{g/l}$	1,5	0,77	1,14	0,28	DK	4,1
Kobber (Cu) filtreret	$\mu\text{g/l}$	1,2	16	8,6	1	DK	8,6
Mangan (Mn)	mg/l	0,024	0,05	0,04	150	DK	0,2
Molybdæn (Mo) filtreret	$\mu\text{g/l}$	6,9	4,7	5,8	6,7	DK	0,9
Nikkel (Ni)	$\mu\text{g/l}$	6,3	5,6	5,95	8,6	EU	0,7
Strontium (Sr)	$\mu\text{g/l}$	390	480	435	2100	DK	0,2
Vanadium (V)	$\mu\text{g/l}$	1,1	2,3	1,7	4,1	DK	0,4
Zink (Zn) filtreret	$\mu\text{g/l}$	17	24	20,5	7,8	DK	2,6
Diethyl hexyl phthalat (DEHP)	$\mu\text{g/l}$	0,12	0,25	0,185	1,3	EU	0,1
Perfluorooctan syre (PFOA)	$\mu\text{g/l}$	0,0079	0,0084	0,0082	$1,30 \cdot 10^{-4}$	EU	62,7
Perfluorooctan sulfonat (PFOS)	$\mu\text{g/l}$	0,0059	0,001	0,0035	$1,30 \cdot 10^{-4}$	EU	26,5
Aminomethylphosphor syre (AMPA)	$\mu\text{g/l}$	2,7	2	2,35	45	Fra ^{a)}	0,1
Glyphosate	$\mu\text{g/l}$	0,55	0,37	0,46	196	Fra ^{b)}	0,0
Total SCCP (C10-C13) excl. LOQ	$\mu\text{g/l}$	0,0119		0,0119	0,4	EU	0,0
ΣRCR							108

a) Water Framework Directive - United Kingdom Technical Advisory Group (WFD-UKTAG) (2010). Proposed EQS for Water Framework Directive Annex VIII substances: glyphosate (For consultation). <https://www.wfduk.org/sites/default/files/Media/Glyphosate%20-%20UKTAG.pdf>

b) Ineris: forslag til EQS for AMPA. <https://substances.ineris.fr/fra/Substance/cas/1066-51-9/3>

DANAK

TEST Reg.nr. 0026

Prøvningsrapport nr.
BWL/194
Side: 1 af 27

Agern Allé 5
2970 Hørsholm

Kalundborg Forsyning A/S

Dokhavnsvej 15
4400 Kalundborg

Att.: Sille Bendix Larsen

Prøvningsrapport nr. [BWL/194](#)

Hermed fremsendes resultater fra den økotoksikologiske test af bromat for Kalundborg Forsyning for kronisk toksiske effekter hos den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*.

Informationer om metode, rådata og statistiske bearbejdede data fremgår af følgende rapport.

Hørsholm, den 30. juni 2020

X

Anja Kamper
Projektleder
Signed by: Anja Kamper

X

Connie Seierø
Laborant
Signed by: Connie Seierø

Prøvningsresultater gælder udelukkende for de(t) prøvede emne(r)
Prøvningsrapporten må kun gengives i uddrag,
såfremt DHI har godkendt uddraget

1 Rapport

Denne rapport omfatter resultater fra test af bromat for kronisk toksiske effekter hos den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*. Testen er udført i overensstemmelse med reglerne for akkrediteret prøvning i overensstemmelse med DS/EN ISO/IEC 17025 /1/ og ISO 16778 /2/ samt protokollen "Testning af bromat for Kalundborg Forsyning med den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*, kronisk test" gengivet i Bilag B. Der var ingen afvigelser fra protokollen.

Testen blev gennemført i perioden fra den 12.06.2020 til 18.06.2020.

Testen blev udført med 99.5% rent natriumbromate (NaBrO_3) fra Sigma-Aldrich (produkt nr. 71325, batch nr. BCBX9200). Teststoffet blev opløst i naturligt havvand som angivet i Bilag B.

Rådata for testen ses i Bilag A tillige med de beregnede effektkoncentrationer. Testresultatet ses desuden i Tabel 1.1. Alle validitetskriterier var opfyldt (se Tabel 1.2).

Tabel 1.1 Resultater af økotoxikologisk test af bromat. 95% konfidensintervaller er angivet i parentes.

Endpoint	NOEC (mg/l)	LOEC (mg/l)	EC/LC10 (mg/l)	EC/LC25 (mg/l)	EC/LC50 (mg/l)
Hatching success	42	>42	>42	>42	>42
Early-life stage mortality	42	>42	>42	>42	>42
Larval development ratio (LDR)	1,3	4,2	1,81 (1,38 – 2,24)	2,97 (2,42 – 3,52)	5,86 (5,02 – 6,70)

Tabel 1.2 ISO 16778 validitetskriterier.

Kriterier	Kravværdi	Opfyldt
"Early-life stage mortality" i kontrolgruppen	$\leq 30\%$ (observeret værdi: 17%)	Ja
"Hatching success" i kontrolgruppen	$\geq 75\%$ (observeret værdi: 97%)	Ja
"Larval development ratio" i kontrolgruppen	$60\% \pm 20\%$ (observeret værdi: 69%)	Ja
Temperaturvariation	Max ± 1 °C (observeret værdi: 18,9-19,3 °C)	Ja
pH variation i kontrolgruppen	≤ 1.0 (observeret værdi: 0,5)	Ja
Iltmætning (i procent)	$\geq 70\%$ throughout test (observeret værdi: $\geq 98\%$)	Ja
Variation i salinitet fra kontrol start (S) værdi	$S \pm \leq 10\%$ (observeret værdi: $32 \text{ ‰} \pm 2$)	Ja
EC50 værdi for referencestoffet 3,5-DCP	$500 \mu\text{g/l} \pm 300 \mu\text{g/l}$ (20 °C and 20 ‰) Observeret: EC50 (24.04.2020): 369 (319-418) $\mu\text{g/l}$ (20 °C and 32 ‰)	Ja

Bilag A

Rådata fra testning med *Acartia tonsa*

A Rådata fra testning af bromat for Kalundborg Forsyning

Tabel A.1 Hæmning af overlevelsen hos *Acartia tonsa*

Control values

Concentration in mg/l	Survival %	Inhibition in per cent
Control 1	70,6	-
Control 2	92,2	-
Control 3	65,7	-
Control 4	89,0	-
Control 5	84,5	-
Control 6	76,4	-
Control 7	90,1	-
Control 8	75,9	-
Control 9	78,3	-
Control 10	95,2	-
Control 11	94,6	-
Control 12	83,3	-
Control mean	83,0	0

Dunnett's test:

NOEC: 42 mg/l
LOEC: >42 mg/l

Data did not allow statistical calculation of the EC values

EC10: >42 mg/l
EC50: >42 mg/l

Experimental data

Concentration in mg/l	Survival %	Inhibition in per cent
0,13	89,9	-8
0,13	91,0	-10
0,13	83,1	0
0,13	90,1	-9
0,13	87,8	-6
0,13	80,6	3
0,42	86,7	-4
0,42	80,6	3
0,42	91,3	-10
0,42	74,1	11
0,42	86,4	-4
0,42	90,5	-9
1,3	84,7	-2
1,3	81,0	2
1,3	81,0	2
1,3	91,7	-10
1,3	88,4	-7
1,3	*	-
4,2	86,7	-4
4,2	84,9	-2
4,2	78,0	6
4,2	89,3	-8
4,2	93,7	-13
4,2	89,2	-8
13	78,1	6
13	95,6	-15
13	75,3	9
13	93,2	-12
13	81,4	2
13	93,9	-13
42	73,1	12
42	85,5	-3
42	82,6	0
42	90,5	-9
42	95,1	-15
42	83,6	-1

*replikatet er udeladt, da filtrering var fejlbehæftet

Tabel A.2
Hæmning af klækning hos *Acartia tonsa*

Control values

Concentration in mg/l	Hatching %	Inhibition in per cent
Control 1	100	-
Control 2	98,5	-
Control 3	100	-
Control 4	97,2	-
Control 5	98,6	-
Control 6	98,6	-
Control 7	95,9	-
Control 8	91,7	-
Control 9	94,3	-
Control 10	95,2	-
Control 11	97,3	-
Control 12	96,7	-
Control mean	97,0	0

Experimental data

Concentration in mg/l	Hatching %	Inhibition in per cent
0,13	97,4	0
0,13	97,0	0
0,13	98,9	-2
0,13	97,1	0
0,13	96,4	1
0,13	98,3	-1
0,42	98,7	-2
0,42	96,8	0
0,42	100	-3
0,42	95,0	2
0,42	96,7	0
0,42	100	-3
1,3	95,9	1
1,3	98,4	-1
1,3	96,8	0
1,3	100	-3
1,3	97,1	0
1,3	*	-
4,2	100	-3
4,2	98,9	-2
4,2	100	-3
4,2	98,8	-2
4,2	96,3	1
4,2	95,5	2
13	98,4	-1
13	100	-3
13	100	-3
13	100	-3
13	98,6	-2
13	95,7	1
42	98,5	-2
42	93,8	3
42	100	-3
42	97,4	0
42	97,6	-1
42	95,3	2

*replikater er udeladt, da filtrering var fejlbehæftet

Dunnett's test:

NOEC: 42 mg/l
LOEC: >42 mg/l

Data did not allow statistical calculation of the EC values

EC10: >42 mg/l
EC50: >42 mg/l

Tabel A.3 Hæmning af larveudvikling (LDR) hos *Acartia tonsa*

Control values

Concentration in mg/l	LDR %	Inhibition in per cent
Control 1	62,5	-
Control 2	72,9	-
Control 3	72,7	-
Control 4	67,7	-
Control 5	78,3	-
Control 6	70,9	-
Control 7	75,0	-
Control 8	61,4	-
Control 9	60,0	-
Control 10	66,7	-
Control 11	80,0	-
Control 12	60,0	-
Control mean	69,0	0

Experimental data

Concentration in mg/l	LDR %	Inhibition in per cent
0,13	71,8	-4
0,13	63,9	7
0,13	83,8	-21
0,13	71,9	-4
0,13	75,0	-9
0,13	76,0	-10
0,42	61,5	11
0,42	60,0	13
0,42	71,2	-3
0,42	69,8	-1
0,42	78,4	-14
0,42	61,4	11
1,3	78,7	-14
1,3	66,7	3
1,3	74,5	-8
1,3	74,5	-8
1,3	68,9	0
1,3	*	-
4,2	44,2	36
4,2	35,6	48
4,2	51,6	25
4,2	37,3	46
4,2	33,8	51
4,2	37,9	45
13	22,0	68
13	27,7	60
13	34,3	50
13	15,9	77
13	17,5	75
13	22,6	67
42	8,2	88
42	7,5	89
42	0,0	100
42	6,0	91
42	3,9	94
42	2,0	97

Dunnett's test:

NOEC: 1,3 mg/l

LOEC: 4,2 mg/l

Data did not allow statistical calculation of the EC values

EC10: 1,81 (1,38 – 2,24) mg/l

EC25: 2,97 (2,42 – 3,52) mg/l

EC50: 5,86 (5,02 – 6,70) mg/l

*repliket er udeladt, da filtrering var fejlbehæftet

Figur 1 Dunnett boxplot af larveudviklingen (LDR) i testen med bromat. Boxplottet viser, at data er normalfordelt i de enkelte testgrupper, samt at testkoncentrationerne 4,2-42 mg/l er signifikant forskellige fra kontrolgruppen ($p < 0.05$).

Figur 2 Effekt på larveudviklingen efter 6 dages eksponering af bromat. Dosis-respons kurven er estimeret ved hjælp af softwareprogrammet R. Den gennemsnitlige hæmning for hver enkelt koncentration og resultatet af den enkelte replikat er vist med hhv. blå og sorte prikker.

Tabel A.4 Rådata fra testen

Concentration (mg/l)		Start			End		
		Eggs and nauplii added		Sum	Eggs	Nauplii	Copepodites
		Eggs	Nauplii	Number	Number	Number	Number
Control	A	66	2	68	0	18	30
Control	B	65	0	65	1	16	43
Control	C	64	3	67	0	12	32
Control	D	72	3	75	2	21	44
Control	E	70	2	72	1	13	47
Control	F	71	2	73	1	16	39
Control	G	73	1	74	3	16	48
Control	H	60	3	63	5	17	27
Control	I	88	0	88	5	26	39
Control	J	63	3	66	3	20	40
Control	K	74	2	76	2	14	56
Control	L	60	2	62	2	20	30
0,13	A	63	2	65	10	53	0
0,13	B	61	2	63	14	47	0
0,13	C	66	2	68	3	64	0
0,13	D	60	0	60	7	48	0
0,13	E	87	1	88	5	80	0
0,13	F	85	0	85	9	72	0
0,42	A	78	3	81	2	20	51
0,42	B	67	2	69	2	22	39
0,42	C	89	1	90	1	12	62
0,42	D	70	3	73	2	18	46
0,42	E	84	1	85	3	18	54
0,42	F	60	3	63	1	12	38
1,3	A	76	0	76	1	25	40
1,3	B	62	2	64	2	20	30
1,3	C	78	2	80	0	21	52
1,3	D	60	1	61	3	13	30
1,3	E	61	0	61	2	11	40
1,3	F	60	3	63	0	22	35
4,2	A	66	2	68	0	18	30
4,2	B	65	0	65	1	16	43
4,2	C	64	3	67	0	12	32
4,2	D	72	3	75	2	21	44
4,2	E	70	2	72	1	13	47
4,2	F	71	2	73	1	16	39
13	A	73	1	74	3	16	48
13	B	60	3	63	5	17	27
13	C	88	0	88	5	26	39
13	D	63	3	66	3	20	40
13	E	74	2	76	2	14	56
13	F	60	2	62	2	20	30
42	A	63	2	65	10	53	0
42	B	61	2	63	14	47	0
42	C	66	2	68	3	64	0
42	D	60	0	60	7	48	0
42	E	87	1	88	5	80	0
42	F	85	0	85	9	72	0

Tabel A.5 pH, ilt og salinitetsmålinger

Testkon- centration (mg/l)	Dato: 12.06.2020 t = 0			Dato: 15.06.2020 t = 3 før tilsætning			Dato: 15.06.2020 t = 3 efter tilsætning			Dato: 18.06.2020 t = 6		
	% O ₂	‰ sal.	pH	% O ₂	‰ sal.	pH	% O ₂	‰ sal.	pH	% O ₂	‰ sal.	pH
Control	100	32,1	7,9	98	32,5	8,4	100	31,6	8,2	100	31,8	8,3
0,13	100	32,1	7,9	98	32,5	8,4	100	31,6	8,3	100	31,8	8,2
0,42	100	32,1	7,9	100	32,5	8,3	100	31,6	8,3	100	31,7	8,3
1,3	100	32,1	7,9	100	32,5	8,4	100	31,8	8,3	100	31,8	8,3
4,2	100	32,1	7,9	100	32,5	8,3	100	31,8	8,3	100	31,9	8,2
13	100	32,1	7,9	100	32,5	8,2	100	31,8	8,2	100	31,9	8,2
42	100	32,1	7,9	100	32,5	8,2	100	31,8	8,2	98	31,8	8,2

Bilag B

Protokol for testning med *Acartia tonsa*

Testning af bromat for Kalundborg Forsyning med den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*, kronisk test

Kalundborg Forsyning

Protokol

Juni 2020

<p>Denne protokol er udarbejdet under DHI's ledelsessystem, som er certificeret af Bureau Veritas for overensstemmelse med ISO 9001 for kvalitetsledelse.</p>	<p>DANAK er omfattet af de multilaterale aftaler for prøvning og kalibrering i European co-operation for Accreditation (EA) samt i International Laboratory Accreditation Cooperation (ILAC) baseret på peer-evaluering. Anvendelse af akkrediteringsmærket på denne protokol er dokumentation for, at ydelsen udføres som en akkrediteret ydelse under virksomhedens DANAK-akkreditering.</p>
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Godkendt af
<p style="text-align: right;">09-06-2020</p> <p>X </p>
<p>Approved by</p> <p>Signed by: Anja Kamper</p>

Testning af bromat for Kalundborg Forsyning med den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*, kronisk test

Protokol

Udarbejdet for Kalundborg Forsyning
Repræsenteret ved Sille Bendix Larsen

DHI laboratorium

Projektleder	Anja Kamper
Kvalitetsansvarlig	Connie Seierø
Projektnummer	11825332
Revision	1.0
Klassifikation	Fortrolig

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BILAG

BILAG A

Analysecertifikat og sikkerhedsdatablad

1 Indledning

Denne protokol omfatter test af bromat for Kalundborg Forsyning for kronisk toksiske effekter hos den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*.

Protokollen beskriver procedurer for test og databehandling. Undersøgelserne gennemføres og rapporteres i overensstemmelse med reglerne for akkrediteret prøvning i overensstemmelse med DS/EN ISO/IEC 17025 /1/ og ISO 16778 /2/ samt under henvisning til nærværende protokol. Rapporterne indeholder bearbejdede primærdata, testresultater i form af tabeller over registreringer og statistisk behandlede data foruden evt. bemærkninger om afvigelser fra denne protokol.

2 Test stof

Testen har til formål at teste den kroniske giftighed af bromat, som dannes under ozonbehandling i renseanlægget hos Kalundborg Forsyning. DHI har derfor indkøbt 99.5% rent Natriumbromate (NaBrO_3) hos Sigma-Aldrich (produkt nr. 71325, batch nr. BCBX9200) til anvendelse i testen. Analysecertifikat og sikkerhedsdatablad er vedhæftet i bilag A.

3 Metoder

3.1 Kronisk toksicitetstest med den marine vandloppe *Acartia tonsa*

Acartia tonsa (DANA) har været holdt i kultur på DHI siden 1987. Kulturen stammer oprindelig fra Nordsøen og er indsamlet af Danmarks Fiskeriundersøgelser. Æg fra denne kultur anvendes i testene.

Testen gennemføres under de samme betingelser som ved kultivering, $20 \pm 1,0^\circ\text{C}$, 16 timer lys og 8 timer mørke. Saliniteten ligger inden for 32 ± 2 PSU.

Som fortyndingsvand anvendes naturligt havvand udtaget fra Nordsøcentrets havvandsindtag. Havvandet filtreres gennem $10 \mu\text{m}/5 \mu\text{m}/0,5 \mu\text{m}/0,22 \mu\text{m}$ filtre.

Natriumbromate bliver testet i følgende koncentrationer: 0; 0,15; 0,5; 1,5; 5; 15 og 50 mg/l svarende til en koncentration af bromat på 0; 0,13; 0,42; 1,3; 4,2; 13 og 42 mg/L.

Derudover opstilles to ekstra replikater af kontrol, laveste og højeste koncentration for at kunne undersøge om det rigtige effektniveau er opnået. Disse replikater aflæses efter 3 dage og de observerede effekter vil danne baggrund for en vurdering af, hvorvidt den rigtige koncentrationsrække er valgt. Resultaterne fra dag 3 vil ikke indgå i den endelige databehandling. Vurderes det at koncentrationsrækken ikke er tilstrækkelig vil testen blive kasseret og en ny test startes med en ny koncentrationsrække.

Testen udføres som semi-statisk test i 250 ml bægerglas (Pyrex). Ved testens start tilsættes 40 ml testopløsning til hvert bægerglas og mellem 60 og 90 *Acartia* æg tilsættes ligeledes. Saltvandsalgen *Rhodomonas salina* anvendes som foder under hele testen i en koncentration på 50,000 celler/ml. På dag 3 tilsættes 40 ml frisklavet testopløsning og alge.

Ved testens afslutning skal den gennemsnitlige andel af copepoditter i kontrollen udgøre 40-80% af summen af nauplier og copepoditter, dvs. larveudviklingsratioen (LDR) skal ligge mellem 0,4 og 0,8. Lugol tilsættes til alle bægerglas og antallet af uklækkede æg, nauplier og copepoditter tælles. pH, ilt og salinitet måles i alle testopløsninger ved start, før og efter tilsætning på dag 3 og ved slut.

Følgende endpoints sammenlignes med kontrolgruppen ved brug af Dunnett's procedure: LDR, klækning, overlevelse. Ved en dosis-respons sammenhæng på et eller flere af disse endpoints bestemmes, hvis muligt, effektkoncentrationerne for 10, 20 og 50% effekt (EC10, EC20 og EC50).

4 Rapportering

Undersøgelserne rapporteres i form af bearbejdede primærdata fra testen. Afvigelser fra protokollen skal i hvert enkelt tilfælde fremgå af rapporten.

5 Referencer

- /1/ DS/EN ISO/IEC 17025: Generelle krav til prøvnings- og kalibreringslaboratoriernes kompetence. 2017.12.19.
- /2/ ISO 16778:2015. "Water quality - Calanoid copepod early-life stage test with *Acartia tonsa*."

BILAG A

Analysecertifikat og sikkerhedsdatablad

Certificate of Analysis

Product Name: SODIUM BROMATE
puriss. p.a., >= 99.5 % RT

Product Number: 71325

Batch Number: BCBX9200

Brand: Sigma-Aldrich

CAS Number: 7789-38-0

Formula: NaBrO₃

Formula Weight: 150.89

Quality Release Date: 03 AUG 2018

Recommended Retest Date: JAN 2023

TEST	SPECIFICATION	RESULT
APPEARANCE (COLOR)	COLORLESS OR WHITE	WHITE
APPEARANCE (FORM)	POWDER OR CRYSTALS	CRYSTALS
REDOX TITRATION	99.5 - 101.0 %	100.0 %
REDOXTITRATION (METHOD)	IODOMETRIC	IODOMETRIC
SOLUBILITY (COLOR)	COLORLESS	COLORLESS
SOLUBILITY (TURBIDITY)	CLEAR	CLEAR
SOLUBILITY (METHOD)	0.5G IN 10ML WATER	0.5G IN 10ML WATER
PH	5.0 - 9.0 (50 MG/ML H(2)O, 25C)	6.3
METAL TRACE ANALYSIS (ICP)	CORRESPONDS TO REQUIREMENTS	PASSED
CALCIUM (ICP)	≤ 10 MG/KG	< 10 MG/KG
CADMIUM (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG
COBALT (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG
CHROMIUM (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG
COPPER (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG
IRON (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG
POTASSIUM (ICP)	≤ 100 MG/KG	< 100 MG/KG
MAGNESIUM (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG
MANGANESE (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG
NICKEL (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG
LEAD (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG
ZINC (ICP)	≤ 5 MG/KG	< 5 MG/KG

Certificate of Analysis

BROMIDE (BR)	≤ 500 MG/KG	< 500 MG/KG
TOTAL NITROGEN	≤ 50 MG/KG	45 MG/KG
SULFATE (SO4)	≤ 500 MG/KG	< 500 MG/KG

Dr. Reinhold Schwenninger
Quality Assurance
Buchs, Switzerland

Sigma-Aldrich warrants that at the time of the quality release or subsequent retest date this product conformed to the information contained in this publication. The current specification sheet may be available at Sigma-Aldrich.com. For further inquiries, please contact Technical Service. Purchaser must determine the suitability of the product for its particular use. See reverse side of invoice or packing slip for additional terms and conditions of sale.

SIKKERHEDSDATABLAD

Udgave 8.2

i henhold til Forordning (EF) nr. 1907/2006

Revisionsdato 28.04.2020

Trykdato 08.06.2020

PUNKT 1: Identifikation af stoffet/blandingen og af selskabet/virksomheden**1.1 Produktidentifikatorer**

Produktnavn	:	Sodium bromate
Produkt nummer	:	71325
Mærke	:	Sigma-Aldrich
REACH No.	:	Registreringsnummer er ikke tilgængelig for dette stof. Stoffet og anvendelse af stoffet er undtaget fra registrering, da der ikke kræves årlige registrering.
CAS-Nr.	:	7789-38-0

1.2 Relevante identificerede anvendelser for stoffet eller blandingen samt anvendelser, der frarådes

Identificerede anvendelser	:	Laboratoriekemikalier, Produktion af stoffer
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1.3 Nærmere oplysninger om leverandøren af sikkerhedsdatabladet

Firma	:	Merck Life Science ApS Vandtårnsvej 62A, DK-2860 SØBORG, DENMARK
Telefon	:	+45 43 56 59-20
Fax	:	+45 43 56 59-05
E-mail adresse	:	TechnicalService@merckgroup.com

1.4 Nødtelefon

Nødtelefonnummer	:	+(45)-69918573 (CHEMTREC) Ved akut udrykning og livsfare - 112
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PUNKT 2: Fareidentifikation**2.1 Klassificering af stoffet eller blandingen****Klassifikation i henhold til regulativ (EC) No 1272/2008**

Brandnærende faste stoffer (Kategori 1), H271

Akut toksicitet, Oralt (Kategori 4), H302

Hudirritation (Kategori 2), H315

Øjenirritation (Kategori 2), H319

For den fuldstændige tekst af faresætningerne nævnt i dette punkt, se punkt 16.

2.2 Mærkningselementer**Mærkning i henhold til regulativ (EC) No 1272/2008**

Piktogram

Signalord	Fare
Faresætning(er)	
H271	Kan forårsage brand eller eksplosion, stærkt brandnærende.
H302	Farlig ved indtagelse.
H315	Forårsager hudirritation.
H319	Forårsager alvorlig øjenirritation.
Præventive sætning(er)	
P210	Holdes væk fra varme, varme overflader, gnister, åben ild og andre antændelseskilder. Rygning forbudt.
P301 + P312 + P330	I TILFÆLDE AF INDTAGELSE: Ring til GIFTLINJEN/læge i tilfælde af ubehag. Skyl munden.
P302 + P352	VED KONTAKT MED HUDEN: Vask med rigeligt vand.
P305 + P351 + P338	VED KONTAKT MED ØJNENE: Skyl forsigtigt med vand i flere minutter. Fjern eventuelle kontaktlinser, hvis dette kan gøres let. Fortsæt skylning.
Supplerende faresætninger	ingen

2.3 Andre farer

Dette stof/blanding indeholder ingen komponenter, der anses for at være enten persistente, bioakkumulerende og toksiske (PBT) eller meget persistente og meget bioakkumulerende (vPvB) ved niveauer på 0,1% eller højere.

PUNKT 3: Sammensætning af/oplysning om indholdsstoffer

3.1 Stoffer

Formel	: BrNaO ₃
Molekylvægt	: 150,89 g/mol
CAS-Nr.	: 7789-38-0
EF-Nr.	: 232-160-4

Komponent	Klassificering	Koncentration
Sodium bromate	Ox. Sol. 1; Acute Tox. 4; Skin Irrit. 2; Eye Irrit. 2; H271, H302, H315, H319	<= 100 %

For den fuldstændige tekst af faresætningerne nævnt i dette punkt, se punkt 16.

PUNKT 4: Førstehjælpsforanstaltninger

4.1 Beskrivelse af førstehjælpsforanstaltninger

Generelle anvisninger

Søg læge. Vis dette sikkerhedsdatablad til vagtlægen.

Hvis det indåndes

Hvis indåndet, flyt tilskadekomne til frisk luft. Hvis ingen vejrtrækning, giv kunstigt åndedræt. Søg læge.

I tilfælde af hudkontakt

Vaskes af med sæbe og rigeligt vand. Søg læge.

I tilfælde af øjenkontakt

Skyl omhyggeligt med rigeligt vand i mindst 15 min. og søg læge.

Ved indtagelse.

Giv aldrig en bevidstløs person noget gennem munden. Skyl munden med vand. Søg læge.

4.2 Vigtigste symptomer og virkninger, både akutte og forsinkede

De vigtigste kendte symptomer og virkninger er beskrevet i mærkning (se afsnit 2,2) og / eller i § 11

4.3 Angivelse af om øjeblikkelig lægehjælp og særlig behandling er nødvendig

Ingen data tilgængelige

PUNKT 5: Brandbekæmpelse**5.1 Slukningsmidler****Egnede slukningsmidler**

Tørt pulver Tørt sand

5.2 Særlige farer i forbindelse med stoffet eller blandingen

Hydrogen bromid gas., Natriumoxid

5.3 Anvisninger for brandmandskab

Benyt om nødvendigt luftforsynet åndedrætsværn ved brandbekæmpelse.

5.4 Yderligere oplysninger

Anvend vandtåge til at køle uåbnede beholdere.

PUNKT 6: Forholdsregler over for udslip ved uheld**6.1 Personlige sikkerhedsforanstaltninger, personlige værnemidler og nødprocedurer**

Brug personligt beskyttelsesudstyr. Undgå støvdannelse. Undgå indånding af dampe/tåge/gas. Sørg for tilstrækkelig ventilation. Evakuer personale til sikre områder. Undgå at indånde støv.

For personlig beskyttelse se punkt 8.

6.2 Miljøbeskyttelsesforanstaltninger

Sørg for at forhindre yderligere lækage eller udslip, hvis det er sikkerhedsmæssigt muligt. Produktet må ikke komme i kloak afløb.

6.3 Metoder og udstyr til inddæmning og oprensning

Fej op og skovl. Opbevar og opsaml spild med en elektrisk beskyttet støvsuger eller ved våd-børstning og placer i affaldsbeholder i henhold til lokale regler (se punkt 13). Opbevares i egnede og lukkede affaldsbeholdere.

6.4 Henvisning til andre punkter

Bortskaffelse se punkt 13.

PUNKT 7: Håndtering og opbevaring**7.1 Forholdsregler for sikker håndtering**

Undgå kontakt med huden og øjnene. Undgå dannelse af støv og aerosoler. Sørg for passende ventilation på steder, hvor støv dannes. Holdes væk fra antændelseskilder - Rygning forbudt. For forholdsregler se afsnit 2,2.

7.2 Betingelser for sikker opbevaring, herunder eventuel uforenelighed

Opbevar beholderen tæt lukket på et tørt og godt ventileret sted. Opbevares køligt.

7.3 Særlige anvendelser

Bortset fra de anvendelser, der er nævnt i afsnit 1,2 er der ingen andre specifikke anvendelser fastsat

PUNKT 8: Eksponeringskontrol/personlige værnemidler

8.1 Kontrolparametre

Indholdsstoffer med grænseværdier

Indeholder ingen stoffer med grænseværdi for erhvervsmæssig eksponering.

8.2 Eksponeringskontrol

Egnede foranstaltninger til eksponeringskontrol

Skal håndteres i overensstemmelse med god erhvervshygiejne og sikkerhedsforanstaltninger. Vask hænder før pauser og ved arbejdstids ophør.

Personlige værnemidler

Beskyttelse af øjne / ansigt

Sikkerhedsbriller med sideskærme i overensstemmelse med EN166 Anvend sikkerhedsbriller testet og godkendt under NIOSH (US) eller EN 166 (EU) standarder.

Beskyttelse af hud

Håndteres med handsker. Handsker skal undersøges inden brug . Brug rigtig teknik til at tage handskens af (uden at røre handskens ydre overflade) for at undgå hudkontakt til dette produkt. Bortskaffelse af forurenede handsker efter brug skal ske i overensstemmelse med gældende lovgivning samt god laboratorie praksis. Vask og tør hænderne.

De valgte beskyttelsehandsker skal opfylde specifikationerne i EUs Forordning 2016/425 samt standarden EN 374, der er afledt deraf.

Fuldstændig kontakt

Materiale: Nitrilgummi

minimumstykkelse: 0,11 mm

Gennemtrængningstid: 480 min

Materiale testet: Dermatril® (KCL 740 / Aldrich Z677272, Størrelse M)

Ved stænk

Materiale: Nitrilgummi

minimumstykkelse: 0,11 mm

Gennemtrængningstid: 480 min

Materiale testet: Dermatril® (KCL 740 / Aldrich Z677272, Størrelse M)

Data kilde: KCL GmbH, D-36124 Eichenzell, Telefon +49 (0)6659 87300, e-mail sales@kcl.de, Test metode: EN374

Hvis det bruges i opløsning, eller blandes med andre stoffer og under forhold som afskiller sig fra EN 374, kontaktes leverandøren af de EC godkendte handsker.

Denne anbefaling er kun vejledende og skal vurderes af en hygiejne- og sikkerhedseksperter der er bekendt med den specifikke anvendelse hos vores kunder. Dette skal ikke fortolkes som en godkendelse til nogen specifikke anvendelses scenarier.

Kropsbeskyttelse

Hel beskyttelsesdragt til beskyttelse mod kemikalier, Typen af beskyttelsesudstyr skal vælges i henhold til koncentrationen og mængden af det farlige stof på det pågældende arbejdssted.

Åndedrætsværn

Hvis risikovurderingen viser, at luftrensede masker er passende, venligst brug en fuld ansigtsmaske type N100 (US), eller type P3 (EN 143) patroner som backup. Hvis åndedrætsværn er det eneste beskyttelsesmiddel, venligst brug en fuld ansigtsmaske. Brug udelukkende åndedrætsværn og komponenter testet og godkendt i henhold til passende lovgivning såsom NIOSH (USA) eller CEN (EU).

Kontrol af miljømæssig eksponering

Sørg for at forhindre yderligere lækage eller udslip, hvis det er sikkerhedsmæssigt muligt. Produktet må ikke komme i kloakafløb.

PUNKT 9: Fysiske og kemiske egenskaber

9.1 Oplysninger om grundlæggende fysiske og kemiske egenskaber

a) Udseende	Form: fast
b) Lugt	lugtfri
c) Lugttærskel	Ingen data tilgængelige
d) pH-værdi	ved 20 °C neutral, Vandopløsning
e) Smeltepunkt/frysepunkt	Smeltepunkt: 381 °C - (nedbrydning)
f) Begyndelseskogepunkt og kogepunktsinterval	Ikke anvendelig
g) Flammepunkt	antændes ikke
h) Fordampningshastighed	Ingen data tilgængelige
i) Antændelighed (fast stof, luftart)	Ingen data tilgængelige
j) Øvre/nedre antændelses- eller eksplosionsgrænser	Ingen data tilgængelige
k) Damptryk	Ingen data tilgængelige
l) Dampmassefylde	Ingen data tilgængelige
m) Relativ massefylde	3,339 g/mL ved 25 °C
n) Vandopløselighed	364 g/l ved 20 °C
o) Fordelingskoefficient: n-oktanol/vand	Ikke anvendelig
p) Selvantændelsestemperatur	Ingen data tilgængelige
q) Dekomponeringstemperatur	>= 381 °C -
r) Viskositet	Ingen data tilgængelige
s) Eksplosive egenskaber	Ingen data tilgængelige
t) Oxiderende egenskaber	Kan forårsage brand eller eksplosion, stærkt brandnærende.

9.2 Anden sikkerhedsinformation

Ingen data tilgængelige

PUNKT 10: Stabilitet og reaktivitet

10.1 Reaktivitet

Ingen data tilgængelige

10.2 Kemisk stabilitet

Stabilt under de anbefalede opbevaringsforhold.

10.3 Risiko for farlige reaktioner

Ingen data tilgængelige

10.4 Forhold, der skal undgås

Ingen data tilgængelige

10.5 Materialer, der skal undgås

Ingen data tilgængelige

10.6 Farlige nedbrydningsprodukter

Farlige dekomponeringsprodukter dannet under brand. - Hydrogen bromid gas., Natriumoxid

Andere farlige dekomponeringsprodukter - Ingen data tilgængelige

I tilfælde af brand: se afsnit 5

PUNKT 11: Toksikologiske oplysninger

11.1 Oplysninger om toksikologiske virkninger

Akut toksicitet

LD50 Oralt - Rotte - 400 mg/kg

Bemærkninger: (ekstern sikkerhedsdatablade)

Hudætsning/-irritation

Alvorlig øjenskade/øjenirritation

Respiratorisk sensibilisering eller hudsensibilisering

Menneskelig erfaring

Resultat: negativ

Bemærkninger: (Lit.)

Kimcellemutagenicitet

Ames test

Resultat: negativ

(HSDB)

Mutagenicitet(pattedyr cell test): micronucleus.

Resultat: positiv

(HSDB)

Kræftfremkaldende egenskaber

IARC: Ingen forbindelse i dette produkt tilstede i mængder større end eller lig 0,1 % er identificeret som sandsynlig, mulig eller bekræftet kræftfremkaldende stof overfor mennesker af IARC.

Reproduktionstoksicitet

Specifik målorgantoksicitet - enkelt eksponering

Akut oral toksicitet - Irritation af slimhinderne i munden, svælget, spiserør og mave-tarmkanalent.

Akut toksicitet ved indånding - Mulige skader:, slimhindeirriterende

Specifik målorgantoksicitet - gentagen eksponering

Aspirationsfare

Yderligere information

RTECS: EF8750000

Efter vores bedste overbevisning er de kemiske, fysiske og toksikologiske forhold ikke undersøgt tilstrækkeligt.

Ved optagelse:

Vi har ingen beskrivelse af toksiske symptomer.

Andre farlige egenskaber kan ikke udelukkes.

Skal håndteres i overensstemmelse med god erhvervshygiejne og sikkerhedsforanstaltninger.

PUNKT 12: Miljøoplysninger

12.1 Toksicitet

12.2 Persistens og nedbrydelighed

Metoderne til at bestemme den biologiske nedbrydelighed kan ikke overføres til uorganiske forbindelser.

12.3 Bioakkumuleringspotentiale

12.4 Mobilitet i jord

12.5 Resultater af PBT- og vPvB-vurdering

Dette stof/blanding indeholder ingen komponenter, der anses for at være enten persistente, bioakkumulerende og toksiske (PBT) eller meget persistente og meget bioakkumulerende (vPvB) ved niveauer på 0,1% eller højere.

12.6 Andre negative virkninger

PUNKT 13: Bortskaffelse

13.1 Metoder til affaldsbehandling

Produkt

Overskud og ikke genanvendelige opløsninger bør leveres til et anerkendt bortskaffelsesfirma. Affald skal bortskaffes i henhold til affaldsdirektiv 2008/98/EF samt øvrige nationale og lokale bestemmelser. Kemikalier skal afleveres i original emballage. Må ikke blandes med andet affald. Urensede beholdere skal håndteres på samme måde som selve produktet.

Forurenede emballage

Bortskaffes som ikke-forarbejdet produkt.

PUNKT 14: Transportoplysninger

14.1 UN-nummer

ADR/RID: 1494

IMDG: 1494

IATA: 1494

14.2 UN-forsendelsesbetegnelse (UN proper shipping name)

ADR/RID: NATRIUMBROMAT

IMDG: SODIUM BROMATE

IATA: Sodium bromate

14.3 Transportfareklasse(r)

ADR/RID: 5.1

IMDG: 5.1

IATA: 5.1

14.4 Emballage gruppe

ADR/RID: II

IMDG: II

IATA: II

14.5 Miljøfarer

ADR/RID: nej

IMDG Marin forureningsfaktor (Marine pollutant): nej

IATA: nej

14.6 Særlige forsigtighedsregler for brugeren

Ingen data tilgængelige

PUNKT 15: Oplysninger om regulering**15.1 Særlige bestemmelser/særlig lovgivning for stoffet eller blandingen med hensyn til sikkerhed, sundhed og miljø**

Dette sikkerhedsdatablad overholder kravene i Forordning (EU) nr. 1907/2006.

15.2 Kemikaliesikkerhedsvurdering

For dette produkt udføres en kemikaliesikkerhedsvurdering .

PUNKT 16: Andre oplysninger**Fuldstændig tekst af faresætninger refereret til under punkt 2 og 3.**

H271	Kan forårsage brand eller eksplosion, stærkt brandnærende.
H302	Farlig ved indtagelse.
H315	Forårsager hudirritation.
H319	Forårsager alvorlig øjenirritation.

Yderligere oplysninger

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Mærket i sidehovedet og/eller sidefoden i dette dokument svarer muligvis midlertidigt ikke visuelt til det erhvervede produkt, mens vi ændrer vores branding. Alle oplysninger i dokumentet vedrørende produktet forbliver dog uændrede og svarer til det bestilte produkt. Hvis du ønsker nærmere oplysninger, bedes du henvende dig til mlsbranding@sial.com.

Sille Bendix Larsen

Kalundborg Forsyning A/S
Dokhavnsvej 15
4400 Kalundborg

Vedr. Akut toksicitetstestning af prøver fra Kalundborg Forsyning med *Daphnia magna***Baggrund**

På baggrund af telefonisk henvendelse og efterfølgende email korrespondance med Sille Bendix Larsen, Kalundborg Forsyning, blev det aftalt, at DTU Miljø skulle gennemføre 48-timers test for akut toksicitet af tre prøver med ferskvandskrebsdyret *Daphnia magna*. Testningen blev aftalt til gennemførelse i januar/februar 2020.

4 March 2020
ABAU

Prøver

De tre prøver (mærket KAL-C3-S1; KAL-C3-S2; KAL-C3-S3) blev modtaget i frosen stand på DTU Miljø i uge 4, 2020. Der blev modtaget fire flasker af hver prøve med ca. 300 mL i hver. De blev opbevaret ved -18 °C og én flaske af hver prøve blev optøet og anvendt til de indledende forsøg. Dernæst blev én flaske af hver prøve optøet og anvendt til toksicitetstestning.

Forsøgsoversigt

For at få et indblik i, om ændringer i pH og iltforhold ville kunne bidrage til en eventuel observeret toksicitet, blev der udført en række forsøg, hvor ilt-indholdet og prøvernes pH blev målt i en 72 timers periode ved henstand i laboratoriet.

Dernæst blev der udført 48-timers toksicitetstest på prøverne i henhold til OECD Guideline for akut dafinetest: OECD (2004). Test No. 202: *Daphnia* sp. Acute Immobilisation Test. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, Paris, France.

Forsøgene blev udført af laborantpraktikant Lea To-Nhu Mæchel og laboratoriefuldsmægtig Susanne Kruse i perioden 19. til 27. Februar 2020.

Indledende forsøg

Iltindholdet og pH blev målt på de optøede prøver. Herefter blev der med regelmæssige mellemrum målt ilt og pH i prøverne i en 30-timers periode og endelig blev værdierne målt efter yderligere henstand i 64 timer. Alle målinger er vist i Tabellerne 1-2 nedenfor.

Der blev observeret meget stabile iltkoncentrationer på mellem 86-88% mætning over hele perioden, og der sås ingen udvikling i disse over tid. Som forventeligt blev en vis pH stigning observeret ved kontakten med atmosfærisk luft - fra en start pH omkring 7.5 til en slut pH på omkring 8.5 efter 94 timers henstand. Der blev observeret hvidligt bundfald i to af prøverne og brunligt bundfald i den tredje. Derfor blev delprøver filtreret og målinger af ilt og pH fortsat på både filterede og ufiltrerede prøver.

Efter ca. 18 timer havde pH stabiliseret sig omkring pH = 8,6 i de ufiltrerede prøver og iltindholdet lå stabilt omkring 85-87% (Tabel 1). For de filterede prøver lå ilt ret stabilt mellem 84-87% og pH lå fra omkring pH = 7,8-8,0 (Tabel 2)

Dermed kan det konkluderes, der ikke var et synderligt iltforbrug i de modtagne prøver, og dafnie-testning ville kunne gennemføres uden iltning. De fundne udsving i pH værdier stemmer overens med en indstilling af ligevægt i karbonat-systemet, og de fundne udfældninger, som var syreopløselige, er højst sandsynligt karbonatsalte. De fundne pH ændringer vil holde sig inden for OECD Guideline's krav til pH udsving under en dafnie-test, og udgør derfor heller ikke et problem i forhold til validiteten af testene.

Toksicitetstesting efter OECD TG 202 med *Daphnia magna*

Efter at have undersøgt prøverne i forhold til pH og ilt, blev der lavet en dafnie test på de filterede prøver (GF/C-filter). Testene blev udført i henhold til OECD TG 202, og der blev udført en "range-finding test" med kun to koncentrationer for hver prøve, nemlig ufortyndede prøver (100% prøve) og 50% fortyndede prøver. Der blev anvendt OECD M7 medie til fortyndingen, hvilket også var mediet for kontrolgruppen. De ufortyndede prøver (100%) blev tilsat salte svarende til koncentrationerne i OECD M7 mediet for at sikre, at de var egnede til dafnie-testning.

Hver koncentration af prøverne blev fordelt på 4 bægerglas med ca. 25 mL i hvert glas. Til hvert glas blev overført 5 dafnier (*Daphnia magna*, DTU/DHI klon), der var <24 timer gamle ved forsøgsstart. Inden selve testen gik i gang, blev der målt pH og O₂ på hver koncentration inkl. kontrol.

Der blev desuden gennemført en test med referencestoffet 3,5 dichlorphenol for at bekræfte, at testenes følsomhed var i overensstemmelse med standardens krav. Dette blev fundet at være tilfældet.

I det testede prøver, bet blev observeret, at pH og ilt lå stabilt på hhv pH omkring 7.9 og ilt-mætning omkring 86-88% både før og efter testen (Tabel 3). Disse værdier overholder validitetskravene til OECD TG 2020 testen.

Efter 24 og 48 timer blev antallet af immobile dafnier talt i hvert glas med prøver fra Kalundborg Forsyning samt i kontrolgruppen. Resultaterne er vist i Tabel 4 i form af observationsdata fra testene. Der blev der ikke observeret immobile dafnier i nogen prøverne, hverken efter 24 eller 48 timers inkubation. Dermed kan det konkluderes, at prøverne ikke er akut toksiske over for *Daphnia magna*.

Vi håber, at disse resultater er anvendelige for Kalundborg Forsyning, og er naturligvis tilgængelig for opklarende spørgsmål mv.

Med venlig hilsen

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads 'Anders Baun'. The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Anders Baun
Professor, Sektionsleder
DTU Miljø

Tabel 1: pH og O₂ målinger på prøver fra Kalundborg forsyning

Uændrede prøver - Ufiltrerede				
Prøvenr.	Dato	Tid	pH	O₂
KAL-C3-S1	19/2 2020	10:00	7,25	88,7
KAL-C3-S1	19/2 2020	11:00	7,55	88,0
KAL-C3-S1	19/2 2020	12:00	7,65	86,2
KAL-C3-S1	19/2 2020	13:00	7,76	86,6
KAL-C3-S1	19/2 2020	14:00	7,88	87,1
KAL-C3-S1	19/2 2020	15:00	7,95	86,8
KAL-C3-S1	20/2 2020	09:00	8,48	86,8
KAL-C3-S1	20/2 2020	10:30	8,53	87,3
KAL-C3-S1	20/2 2020	16:00	8,60	87,1
Prøvenr.	Dato	Tid	pH	O₂
KAL-C3-S2	19/2 2020	10:00	7,46	87,7
KAL-C3-S2	19/2 2020	11:00	7,65	87,2
KAL-C3-S2	19/2 2020	12:00	7,73	84,2
KAL-C3-S2	19/2 2020	13:00	7,83	85,7
KAL-C3-S2	19/2 2020	14:00	7,89	86,5
KAL-C3-S2	19/2 2020	15:00	7,97	86,2
KAL-C3-S2	20/2 2020	09:00	8,40	86,9
KAL-C3-S2	20/2 2020	10:30	8,44	86,9
KAL-C3-S2	20/2 2020	16:00	8,51	86,9
Prøvenr.	Dato	Tid	pH	O₂
KAL-C3-S3	19/2 2020	10:00	7,42	86,6
KAL-C3-S3	19/2 2020	11:00	7,62	85,9
KAL-C3-S3	19/2 2020	12:00	7,72	85,0

Tabel 1 - fortsat: pH og O₂ målinger på prøver fra Kalundborg forsyning

Uændrede prøver - Ufiltrerede				
Prøvenr.	Dato	Tid	pH	O₂
KAL-C3-S1	21/2 2020	8:00	8,59	87,0
KAL-C3-S1	21/2 2020	12:00	8,64	86,4
KAL-C3-S1	21/2 2020	15:00	8,65	85,5
KAL-C3-S1	21/2 2020	16:00	8,65	86,0
KAL-C3-S1	24/2 2020	8:20	8,68	87,0
Prøvenr.	Dato	Tid	pH	O₂
KAL-C3-S2	21/2 2020	8:00	8,56	87,0
KAL-C3-S2	21/2 2020	12:00	8,60	86,2
KAL-C3-S2	21/2 2020	15:00	8,60	85,4
KAL-C3-S2	21/2 2020	16:00	8,60	85,8
KAL-C3-S2	24/2 2020	8:20	8,64	86,4
Prøvenr.	Dato	Tid	pH	O₂
KAL-C3-S3	21/2 2020	8:00	8,64	86,8
KAL-C3-S3	21/2 2020	12:00	8,66	86,0
KAL-C3-S3	21/2 2020	15:00	8,66	85,1
KAL-C3-S3	21/2 2020	16:00	8,66	85,6
KAL-C3-S3	24/2 2020	8:20	8,71	86,7

Tabel 2: pH og O₂ målinger på prøver fra Kalundborg forsyning – filtrerede prøver

Uændrede prøver - Filtrerede				
Prøvenr.	Dato	Tid	pH	O₂
KAL-C3-S1	21/2 2020	8:00	7,79	86,9
KAL-C3-S1	21/2 2020	12:00	7,84	86,4
KAL-C3-S1	21/2 2020	15:00	7,88	84,9
KAL-C3-S1	21/2 2020	16:00	7,89	84,6
KAL-C3-S1	24/2 2020	8:20	8,33	87,7
Prøvenr.	Dato	Tid	pH	O₂
KAL-C3-S2	21/2 2020	8:00	7,94	86,7
KAL-C3-S2	21/2 2020	12:00	7,97	86,1
KAL-C3-S2	21/2 2020	15:00	8,00	84,4
KAL-C3-S2	21/2 2020	16:00	8,02	85,2
KAL-C3-S2	24/2 2020	8:20	8,36	87,3
Prøvenr.	Dato	Tid	pH	O₂
KAL-C3-S3	21/2 2020	8:00	7,84	87,0
KAL-C3-S3	21/2 2020	12:00	7,87	86,1
KAL-C3-S3	21/2 2020	15:00	7,91	84,5
KAL-C3-S3	21/2 2020	16:00	7,92	84,7
KAL-C3-S3	24/2 2020	8:20	8,00	87,2

Tabel 3. pH og O₂ målinger for dafnie test af prøver fra Kalundborg Forsyning

100% prøve		
Prøve	pH	O ₂
KAL-C3-S1	7,86	86,5
KAL-C3-S2	7,89	85,5
KAL-C3-S3	7,89	86,0

50% prøve		
Prøve	pH	O ₂
KAL-C3-S1	7,92	87,7
KAL-C3-S2	7,94	87,4
KAL-C3-S3	7,93	87,5

Kontrol	
pH	O ₂
7,74	87,6

Tabel 4: Observationsdata fra OECD 202 Dafnie test udført på prøver fra Kalundborg Forsyning

Prøve	Dafnier pr. koncentration	Antal dafnier pr. bægerglas	Antal immobile efter 24 timer	Totalt antal immobile efter 24 timer	Antal immobile efter 48 timer	Totalt immobile døde efter 48 timer
Kontrol	20	A = 5 B = 5 C = 5 D = 5	A = 0 B = 0 C = 1* D = 0	1*	A = 0 B = 0 C = 1 D = 0	1*
KAL-C3-S1 100%	20	A = 5 B = 5 C = 5 D = 5	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0
KAL-C3-S2 100%	20	A = 5 B = 5 C = 5 D = 5	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0
KAL-C3-S3 100%	20	A = 5 B = 5 C = 5 D = 5	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0
KAL-C3-S1 50%	20	A = 5 B = 5 C = 5 D = 5	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0
KAL-C3-S2 50%	20	A = 5 B = 5 C = 5 D = 5	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0
KAL-C3-S3 50%	20	A = 5 B = 5 C = 5 D = 5	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0	A = 0 B = 0 C = 0 D = 0	0

* Dafnien sad oppe på siden af glasset og ikke nede i mediet og var derfor ikke immobil på grund af prøven.

Review of chronic toxicity tests of samples from Kalundborg Forsyning.

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Executive summary

A series of ecotoxicity for chronic effects towards the freshwater crustacean *Ceriodaphnia dubia* was carried out on samples from the wastewater treatment plant of Kalundborg Forsyning. The samples were collected at the three different sampling points on three different occasions and tested by the Latvian Institute of Aquatic Ecology.

This review evaluates the results obtained in terms of a. The compliance of the performed tests with the ISO standard (ISO 20665:2008 Water Quality – Determination of chronic toxicity to *Ceriodaphnia dubia*) and b. Interpretation of the test results with regards to mortality and reproduction of *C. dubia* exposed to samples from Kalundborg Forsyning.

The major findings of the review are:

- All tests were in compliance with the test conditions and validity criteria of the ISO standard.
- A general increase in pH beyond the ranges specified in the ISO standard was observed. Whether this has influenced the outcome of the toxicity tests could not be determined using the data available.
- In all samples, a significant mortality of exposed animals was found. Mortality mainly occurred after 96 hours of testing. Therefore, regulatory relevant values for acute toxicity (e.g. LC₅₀-values with duration of 24h to 96h) cannot be derived from the data.
- Reproductive effects, in terms of reduced number of offspring per mother animal, were recorded for all samples. However, the high mortality among exposed animals hampers definitive conclusions regarding reproductive toxicity.

Background

DTU Environment, represented by professor Anders Baun, got approached by Sille Bendix Larsen, Kalundborg Forsyning, the 17th of March 2020 with regards to performing an independent peer review of the toxicity tests carried out by Latvian Institute of Aquatic Ecology on water samples from Kalundborg wwtp using the test

method ISO 20665: 2008 Water quality — Determination of chronic toxicity to *Ceriodaphnia dubia*.

The 18th of March 2020, DTU Environment accepted to perform the review. Kalundborg Forsyning accepted to pay for this service while not interfering with the outcome of the review.

Data available

The data available for the review is the pdf-version of a PowerPoint presentation by the Latvian Institute of Aquatic Ecology (by Leva Barda, Ineta Liepina, Vita Plivča, Laura Dzintare, Leva Putna-Nimane) in Appendix 1, and the raw data provided by the Latvian Institute of Aquatic Ecology in the form of an Excel sheet, Appendix 2.

Scope of review

This review will focus on:

1. The compliance of the performed tests with the ISO standard (ISO 20665:2008 Water Quality – Determination of chronic toxicity to *Ceriodaphnia dubia*) including the validity of the tests carried out by comparing to validity criteria as defined in the ISO standard.
2. Providing an overview of the test results and the interpretation of these with regards to reproductive effects on *C. dubia*
3. Summary and conclusions on the outcome of the testing in terms of mortality and reproduction of *C. dubia* exposed to samples from Kalundborg Forsyning.

1. Compliance with ISO standard and validity of tests

Table 1.1 compares the tests carried out with the test conditions and validity criteria defined in ISO 20665:2008. From this it is evident that, with the exception of the increase in pH during incubation, the tests are in compliance with the ISO standard. The results are as such considered to be valid, but with the comment that the increase in pH may contribute to explaining the outcome of the tests (mainly with regards to mortality among mother animals see section 2)

Table 1.1 Parameters defined by ISO 20665:2008, description of the parameter and evaluation of compliance with the ISO standard in the tests carried out.

Parameter	Description	Compliance with ISO 20665:2008
Duration	The test duration is specified by ISO as 7 ± 1 d. The final duration is decided as the time when 60% of the control organisms have produced their 3 rd brood. For the test carried out, the meant that all tests had a duration of 8 days. For two samples a duration of 7 days would be appropriate as clearly written in Appendix 3.	Yes
Organism age	< 24 h old organisms used at the beginning of the test. Organisms should be taken from cultures run for at least three generations and taken from a brood with at least 8 neonates. These details are not given specifically in the materials review, but assumed to be fulfilled as a part of a general good laboratory procedure of the <i>Ceriodaphnia</i> testing.	(Yes)
Temperature	The standard specifies a temperature of 25 ± 2 °C. In Appendix 2 the temperatures are recorded to be in the range of 23-24 °C	Yes
Oxygen	Oxygen levels are in the range of 7-8 mgO ₂ /L (Appendix 2)	Yes
pH	The ISO standard specifies that a pH drift of ≤ 0.3 pH units is acceptable during incubation. In general an increase in pH is noted in the tests carried out. From the initial pH around pH 7.8 increases in pH was recorded during the incubation for all test concentrations. At the lower concentrations of sample the increase was about 0.5 pH unit and at the higher concentrations increases of 1.0-1.3 pH units were observed.	No
Reference substance	The ISO standard specifies that the following test substances are acceptable as reference substances (positive controls): NaPCP, CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O, NaCl, ZnSO ₄ . Data on reference toxicants was not available for this review but is assumed to be present as a part of a general good laboratory procedure of the <i>Ceriodaphnia</i> testing.	(Yes)
Test concentrations and replicates	The ISO standard prescribes the use of at least five test concentrations separated by a factor <3.2 and a control group – all with 10 replicates per concentrations. This is identical to the test setup used here.	Yes

Table 1.1 – continued Parameters defined by ISO 20665:2008, description of the parameter and evaluation of compliance with the ISO standard in the tests carried out.

Parameter	Description	Compliance with ISO 20665:2008
Medium renewal and feeding	No information was provided on medium renewal and feeding in the data available, but this assumed to be carried out according to section 9.5 in the ISO standard as a part of a general good laboratory procedure of the <i>Ceriodaphnia</i> testing.	(Yes)
Expression of results	The results shown in Appendix 2 are expressed in terms of EC ₅₀ values for reproduction using an appropriate model in compliance with the ISO standard.	Yes
Validity criteria for controls		
Mortality	The mortality in the control groups do not exceed the maximum of 20% stated by ISO. Therefore, the tests are valid in this respect	Yes
Proportion of males	The proportion of adult males must not exceed 10%. This is not specifically mentioned in the material provided but assumed to be fulfilled as a part of a general good laboratory procedure of the <i>Ceriodaphnia</i> testing.	(Yes)
Number of broods	In all tests, three broods were produced by the end of the tests	Yes
Mean number of offspring	The mean number of offspring per alive female at the end of the test should be ≥ 15 .	Yes

(Yes): Indicates that data were not available for the evaluation but are assumed to be in place as a part of a general good laboratory procedure for testing of chronic effects towards *Ceriodaphnia dubia*.

2. Test results and their interpretation with regards to reproductive effects in *C. dubia*

2.1 Brief description of the experiments carried out

Samples were collected at three sampling points (S1-S3) at the wastewater treatment plant of Kalundborg Forsyning. Three sampling campaigns (C1, C2, and C4) were carried out. This means that a total of 9 different samples from Kalundborg Forsyning were tested for chronic toxicity towards *C. dubia*.

The samples were diluted to obtain the five test concentrations: 98.87%, 49.34%, 24.67, 12.34%, 6.15%. The tests were carried out in accordance with the ISO standard 20665:2008. Ten replicates (each with one *C. dubia*, henceforth named mother animals) were used for each concentration and for the control group. The survival of the mother animals and the number of neonates were counted daily in a 8 days testing period.

The main results of the tests in terms of mortality of mother animals and reproductive effects in terms of number of offsprings were summarized by Barda et al. (2019), Appendix 1. Furthermore, the raw data provided in Appendix 2 has been reviewed and summary tables have been established in this review to provide an overview of the results obtained.

2.2 Mortality of *C. dubia* mother animals during testing for reproductive effects

As described by Barda et al. (2019), Appendix 1, several of the mother animals died during the 8 days of testing when exposed to the samples. However, the survival ratios in the control groups were within the validity criteria of the ISO standard as mentioned in Table 1.1.

For samples S1-S3 from the 2nd sampling campaign (C2), Barda et al., (2019), Appendix 1, illustrated the mortality during the 8 days of testing for all concentrations of S1-S3 in Figure 2.1.

***Ceriodaphnia dubia*, reproduction inhibition 7±1d**

>80% mortality of adult females after first 24h were detected at 98.87% concentration for samples S2, S3.

Figure 2.1. Number of surviving adult *C. dubia* during an 8 days exposure to three samples from Kalundborg Forsyning (sample numbers S1, S2, S3). Samples from second sampling campaign C2. Source: Slide 13 in Appendix 1.

It is observed that for all samples, no mother animals were alive after days of exposure to the highest test concentration 98.87% sample. For the data shown in Figure 2.1, the mortality generally followed a concentration-response pattern with 80-100% mortality in the second highest test concentration (49.34% sample) at day 8 and reduced mortality at lower concentrations (from 20-60% mortality for all samples). The least mortality was observed at the lowest sample concentration (6.15% sample) with 20% mortality for all samples, i.e. two of the ten mother animals were no longer alive after 8 days of exposure to S1-S3 collected in the second sampling campaign (C2).

Only for the highest concentration, mortality was observed within the first 96 hours of testing with the exception of sample 2 from the 2nd sampling campaign, where 1 animal died within the first 24 hours of exposure to 49.34 % sample. This means that estimates of LC_{50, 96h} (or similar) cannot be derived from the data set from the C2 sampling campaign.

This pattern of high mortality in the 8-d reproduction test was also seen in samples from the two other sampling campaigns (C1 and C4) as evidenced by the numbers provided in Appendix 2. For the sake of completeness, all mortality data – in terms of number surviving mothers at day 8 - are shown in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1. Number of surviving mother animals (*C. dubia*) after 8 days of testing. The results are shown for the controls and all the concentrations (6.15%-98.87%) of the three samples from Kalundborg Forsyning (S1-S3) from the three different sampling campaigns (C1, C2, C4). Ten living mother animals were used for each sample and at each concentration at day 0. Shaded cells indicate sample dilutions at which less than 80% of the mother animals survived the 8 days exposure. Data is collected for this review based on Appendix 2.

Sample	Campaign	Concentration (in percent sample)					
		Control	6.15%	12.34%	24.67%	49.34%	98.87%
S1	C1	10	6	6	10	5	0
	C2	10	8	8	7	1	0
	C4	10	8	7	8	5	0
S2	C1	8	8	5	6	0	0
	C2	8	8	5	6	0	0
	C4	10	8	7	6	3	0
S3	C1	9	2	1	2	4	0
	C2	10	8	6	4	2	0
	C4	10	7	6	3	1	0

As it was the case for samples from C2 (Figure 2.1), significant mortality (>30% and often 40-50%) was observed at samples concentrations 12.34-98.87% for all samples. Furthermore, 100% mortality was observed at the highest sample concentration for all samples (Table 2.1). For three samples (S1_C1; S3_C1; S3_C4) even the lowest tested concentration (6.15%) gave rise to >40% mortality among mother animals at day 8.

Similar to the data for C2 (Figure 2.1) it was only for the highest concentration that significant mortality (>20%) was observed within the first 96 hours of testing. Estimates of LC_{50,96h} (or similar) can therefore not be derived from the data sets from sampling campaigns C1 and C4.

While the increase in pH mentioned in Table 1.1 may have contributed to the mortality of the mother animals and may be indicative of effects related to the sample matrix (e.g. the high alkalinity for samples from Kalundborg Forsyning), it is outside the scope of this review to speculate on possible modes of toxicity of the samples.

2.3. Effects on reproduction of *C. dubia*

Figure 2.2 summarizes the findings of tests with regards to reproduction of *C. dubia* exposed to samples S1-S3 from sampling campaigns C1 and C2. Data for the 3rd sampling campaign (C4) was not included in the presentation by Barda et al. (2019), Appendix 1, Figure 2.2, but is available in the raw data provided (Appendix 2). For the sake of completeness, all data – in terms of average number of offspring per mother at day 8 - are shown in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 Average number of offspring per mother animal after 8 days of testing – all mother animals considered. The results are shown for the controls and all the concentrations (6.15%-98.87%) of the three samples from Kalundborg Forsyning (S1-S3) in the three different test sampling campaigns (C1, C2, C4) after 8 days of incubation. Data are collected for this review based on Appendix 2.

Sample	Test	Concentration					
		Control	6.15%	12.34%	24.67%	49.34%	98.87%
S1	C1	20.4	16.7	8.5	10.1	5	0
	C2	20.2	15	13.9	10.7	3.3	0
	C4	20.8	17	12.1	10.5	4.2	0
S2	C1	27.1	19	17.9	9.9	6.4	0
	C2	20.3	14	13.3	13.5	1.4	0
	C4	20.5	18	15.6	11.6	4.7	0
S3	C1	17.2	4	3.8	4.3	3.3	0
	C2	20.2	10.4	10.1	8	2.8	0
	C4	20.8	9.7	9.6	6.9	3.8	0

A
Crustacea (reproduction inhibition) (*Ceriodaphnia dubia*)

Kalunburg_C1

B
Crustacea (reproduction inhibition) (*Ceriodaphnia dubia*)

Kalunburg_C2

Figure 2.2. Total number of offspring of *C. dubia* after a 8 days exposure to three samples from Kalunborg Forsyning (sample numbers S1, S2, S3). A: First test run C1; B: Second test run C2. Source: A – slide 11 in Appendix 1; B – slide 12 in Appendix 1

Based on the results in Figure 2.2, Barda et al. (2019) – Appendix 1 - presented the lowest observed effective concentrations shown in Table 2.3. No LOEC values for samples from sampling campaign C4 have been presented. In Appendix 2, EC₅₀ values are presented for the dataset shown in Table 2.2. These EC₅₀ values are also included in table 2.3

Table 2.3 Lowest observed effective concentrations (LOEC) and EC₅₀ values based on number of offspring per mother animal (*C. dubia*) after 8 days exposure to three samples from Kalundborg Forsyning (sample numbers S1, S2, S3). All numbers are in % sample. Numbers in brackets are 95% confidence intervals. Source for LOECs: Slide 14 and 15 in Appendix 1; Source for EC₅₀ values: Appendix 2.

Sample no.	LOEC		EC ₅₀		
	Sampling campaign		Sampling campaign		
	C1	C2	C1	C2	C4
S1	12.34	6.15	15.78 [11.97;20.80]	20.09 [14.86;26.42]	18.84 [14.83;23.88]
S2	6.15	6.15	16.44 [12.25;22.08]	20.18 [14.8;26.49]	25.35 [20.28;31.70]
S3	6.15	6.15	0.52* [0.01;21.28]	9.50 [6.44; 4.00]	7.39 [5.07;0.76]

*Extrapolated value. Lowest tested concentration is 6.15%

From Table 2.3 LOEC-values from the 8-d reproduction test with *C. dubia* were found to be 6.15 % sample based on observation for all samples for both test sampling campaigns, except for sample S1 in the first test run, where a LOEC of 12.34% was observed.

The EC₅₀-values estimated based on number of offspring per mother animal when considering all mother animals show that from 7.4% to 25.3% caused a 50% decrease in the reproductive output (Table 2.3). For S3_C1 an EC₅₀ of 0.52% (with large confidence intervals) was estimated. This value is an extrapolated value, far below the lowest tested concentration, and cannot be used.

As shown above, in Table 2.1, a very low number of mother animals survived the 8 days of exposure to sample S3_C1. Therefore, the reproduction data for this sample should not be interpreted as reproductive toxicity but rather as mortality. This is in fact a general pattern in the reproduction data:

The high to very high mortality in all samples at all concentrations above 6.15% (Table 2.1) raises serious concerns with regards to the usability of the effect values for reproductive toxicity (LOEC and EC50) listed in Table 2.3.

The ISO standard 20665:2008 does in fact only set up criteria for survival of control animal ($\geq 80\%$ at the end of the test) and not for survival of mother animals in the exposed replicates. However, since dead animals do not reproduce, it would in this reviewer's opinion not be correct to interpret results from concentrations with high replicate mortality as reproductive toxicity. A further analysis of the data based on number of surviving mother animals is added in Annex 1.

3. Summary and conclusions

A series of *Ceriodaphnia dubia* reproduction tests were carried out on samples collected at the wastewater plant of Kalundborg Forsyning in accordance with the ISO standard ISO20665:2008. Except for a general increase in pH beyond the ranges specified in the ISO standard, the performance of all tests was found to be in compliance with the test conditions and validity criteria of the ISO standard. The data is therefore considered as regulatory relevant and reliable.

For all samples, a significant mortality of exposed animals were found after 8 days of exposure. The mortality main occurred after 96 hours of testing and regulatory relevant LC50-values (i.e. with duration of 24h to 96h) cannot be derived from the data.

While apparent reproductive effects, in terms of reduced number of offspring per mother animal, were recorded for all samples, the high to very high mortality among exposed mother animals makes definitive conclusions regarding reproductive toxicity very uncertain.

In general, only results from the lowest of the five concentrations used can be interpreted in terms of reproductive toxicity. It would have been appropriate to use lower exposure concentrations once mortality among mother animals exposed to samples at high concentrations was observed. However, a data analysis, with a strong emphasis on statistical analysis, may be carried out on the existing data corrected for mortality among exposed mother animals.

4. References

ISO 20665:2008. Water Quality – Determination of chronic toxicity to *Ceriodaphnia dubia*. International Standardization Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Barda, L., Liepina, I., Plivča, V., Dzintare, L., Putna-Nimane, L. (2019). the pdf-version of a PowerPoint presentation by the Latvian Institute of Aquatic Ecology.

Appendix 2. Raw data provided by the Latvian Institute of Aquatic Ecology in the form of an Excel sheet.

Annex 1. Expression of reproductive results in terms of surviving mothers

In scientific papers reporting the outcome of reproduction tests with crustaceans, it is common practise to express the results both in terms of numbers of offspring per mother animal (as shown in Table 2.2) and in terms of number of offspring per surviving mother at the end of the testing.

The data shown in Table A1 combines the mortality data of Table 2.1 and the reproductive data of Table 2.2, showing the average number of offspring per surviving mother animal. The shaded cells in Table A1 indicate sample dilutions where significant mortality (>20%) of mother animals occurred. This means that the number of replicates is less than 8 (from 1 to 7 surviving mothers, see Tabel 2.1) and the statistical power of the results is reduced significantly.

This makes an estimation of EC-values more uncertain, though it may be attempted placing higher emphasis on 95% confidence intervals than on the actual EC-values. With regards to LOEC values, the pattern shown in Table A1 will for some samples result in higher LOECs – but again the test for statistical significance will be supported by fewer replicates than optimal.

Table A1. Average number of offspring per surviving number of mother animals after 8 days of testing. The results are shown for the controls and all the concentrations (6.15%-98.87%) of the three samples from Kalundborg Forsyning (S1-S3) from the three different sampling campaigns (C1, C2, C4). Shaded cells indicate sample dilutions at which less than 80% of the mother animals survived the 8 days exposure. Data is collected for this review based on Appendix 2.

Sample	Test	Concentration					
		Control	6.15%	12.34%	24.67%	49.34%	98.87%
S1	C1	20.4	19.7	9.7	8.3	6.0	-
	C2	20.2	15.9	15.8	14.1	10.0	-
	C4	20.8	19.0	13.1	12.3	6.2	-
S2	C1	29.0	20.7	16.8	9.9	10.7	-
	C2	20.3	14.0	14.3	13.5	-	-
	C4	20.5	20.4	18.0	12.8	7.0	-
S3	C1	17.1	9.0	3.8	5.0	4.0	-
	C2	20.2	10.6	11.0	12.0	5.5	-
	C4	20.8	11.3	11.0	12.0	2.0	-

- : No mother animals alive at Day 8